

Experiment Group	Group_Typ	Group_Des	Animal	Time_Point	Time_Point	Trial	Trial_Descr
CatWalk_1 Sham-WT	Sham		J1	PID 346		Trial0001	
CatWalk_1 Sham-WT	Sham		J26	PID 346		Trial0002	
CatWalk_1 Sham-WT	Sham		1	PID 346		Trial0003	
CatWalk_1 Sham-WT	Sham		2	PID 346		Trial0004	
CatWalk_1 Sham-WT	Sham		3	PID 346		Trial0005	
CatWalk_1 Sham-WT	Sham		4	PID 346		Trial0006	
CatWalk_1 Sham-WT	Sham		5	PID 346		Trial0007	
CatWalk_1 Sham-WT	Sham		6	PID 346		Trial0008	
CatWalk_1 Sham-WT	Sham		7	PID 346		Trial0009	
CatWalk_1 Sham-WT	Sham		8	PID 346		Trial0010	
CatWalk_1 Sham-KO	Sham		6677	PID 346		Trial0011	
CatWalk_1 Sham-KO	Sham		6678	PID 346		Trial0012	
CatWalk_1 Sham-KO	Sham		6679	PID 346		Trial0013	
CatWalk_1 Sham-KO	Sham		6680	PID 346		Trial0014	
CatWalk_1 Sham-KO	Sham		6681	PID 346		Trial0015	
CatWalk_1 Sham-KO	Sham		792	PID 346		Trial0016	
CatWalk_1 Sham-KO	Sham		793	PID 346		Trial0017	
CatWalk_1 Sham-KO	Sham		KO-1	PID 346		Trial0018	
CatWalk_1 Sham-KO	Sham		KO-2	PID 346		Trial0019	
CatWalk_1 Sham-KO	Sham		KO-3	PID 346		Trial0020	
CatWalk_1 SCI-WT	Experiment		J11	PID 346		Trial0021	
CatWalk_1 SCI-WT	Experiment		J12	PID 346		Trial0022	
CatWalk_1 SCI-WT	Experiment		J14	PID 346		Trial0023	
CatWalk_1 SCI-WT	Experiment		J16	PID 346		Trial0024	
CatWalk_1 SCI-WT	Experiment		J17	PID 346		Trial0025	
CatWalk_1 SCI-WT	Experiment		J18	PID 346		Trial0026	
CatWalk_1 SCI-WT	Experiment		J19	PID 346		Trial0027	
CatWalk_1 SCI-WT	Experiment		J20	PID 346		Trial0028	
CatWalk_1 SCI-KO	Experiment		6645	PID 346		Trial0029	
CatWalk_1 SCI-KO	Experiment		6646	PID 346		Trial0030	
CatWalk_1 SCI-KO	Experiment		6648	PID 346		Trial0031	
CatWalk_1 SCI-KO	Experiment		6650	PID 346		Trial0032	
CatWalk_1 SCI-KO	Experiment		6660	PID 346		Trial0033	
CatWalk_1 SCI-KO	Experiment		6663	PID 346		Trial0034	
CatWalk_1 SCI-KO	Experiment		6666	PID 346		Trial0035	

NumberOf	Run_Durati	Run_Avera	Run_Maxin	RF_Stand_(	RF_StandIn	RF_MaxCoi	RF_MaxCoi	RF_MaxCoi
4	3.396581	20.86829	59	0.197511	-9.82601	56.73675	0.18668	106.24
5	3.169646	24.81363	57.8	0.17365	-9.06293	44.65121	0.223668	124.1
3	4.049163	13.54154	42	0.181129	-4.36754	44.90113	0.098228	69.35484
3	4.166029	12.68511	65	0.226745	-2.39343	28.23269	0.30574	140.3333
3	2.69347	23.87204	22	0.16329	-6.84806	37.83711	0.332845	165.4211
3	2.658444	20.76976	14	0.17992	-5.62334	43.29093	0.351119	175.8333
5	5.355182	10.05568	83.6	0.351088	-2.47562	38.83036	0.22338	135.0732
3	3.454985	16.8339	42.66667	0.234372	-4.05258	42.55556	0.229807	140.9412
5	3.483538	15.11674	55.8	0.228354	-3.48933	26.45077	0.314232	166.7027
3	4.508735	14.6713	89.33333	0.292059	-5.03379	35.65256	0.276661	140
4	3.619508	14.96108	40.25	0.233977	-4.26772	36.52385	0.289216	144.0714
5	4.321087	19.02211	59	0.317118	-4.05102	37.37946	0.309964	155.3158
6	3.275049	16.42737	80.5	0.213473	-5.50797	33.58935	0.3131	144.6087
3	1.858486	28.36503	25.66667	0.109355	-7.47737	33.27813	0.32491	151.8333
3	3.777293	14.07246	25.33333	0.243405	-3.98585	52.49076	0.253635	117.5789
5	2.087532	24.38156	32	0.124923	-6.44311	33.3381	0.2594	124.5313
3	2.286193	22.78406	40.66667	0.140293	-7.71654	46.81691	0.200794	125.55
5	1.771882	29.75794	32.2	0.125394	-8.37241	35.73187	0.280862	138.8571
5	4.23237	24.85962	97.4	0.311718	-8.86838	36.92466	0.23491	128.6818
4	1.929076	27.93894	54.25	0.126119	-10.4408	38.52338	0.270075	140.0385
3	4.996293	10.78255	59.66667	0.308869	-4.29412	48.80289	0.184313	126.9545
3	1.944727	26.67637	14.66667	0.135243	-6.68181	37.41443	0.272437	142.125
3	3.325277	15.88095	42.66667	0.236788	-4.46414	32.77043	0.338649	142.7143
3	4.665566	14.65326	75.33333	0.227291	-2.95281	32.10261	0.323766	138.92
3	2.393457	20.88064	39.33333	0.14461	-5.90669	40.49793	0.270798	137.9091
3	2.097671	24.85932	11.66667	0.133013	-5.45013	33.42807	0.30781	154.4737
5	3.69082	15.12724	68.2	0.311433	-3.97716	45.13222	0.326629	159.5806
3	2.895462	19.70082	67	0.183796	-5.0897	39.03566	0.345857	171.6471
3	2.283166	25.46483	21	0.174163	-6.18679	29.72867	0.352967	154.4706
3	2.104916	24.29669	24.66667	0.162166	-3.89504	30.95399	0.335064	155.6875
5	4.369755	13.06462	72	0.245852	-3.87065	37.01222	0.302689	142.439
3	2.388437	21.74055	29.66667	0.169904	-4.15782	23.39887	0.362829	163
3	2.016523	25.29388	13.33333	0.136066	-3.91871	29.02516	0.33346	154.5263
3	3.521921	15.30873	33.66667	0.195032	-3.5342	34.14918	0.320491	146.3
5	5.002589	12.61367	65.8	0.289865	-2.92363	31.0262	0.366109	174

RF_MaxCo	RF_PrintLe	RF_PrintWi	RF_PrintAr	RF_MaxInt	RF_MaxInt	RF_MinInt	RF_MeanIr	RF_MeanIr
60.55088	0.72612	0.594548	0.241421	65.85961	109.56	37.4	64.02582	89.00614
64.78075	0.758448	0.681514	0.277603	56.29067	132.0333	37.46667	67.82455	101.7389
38.47731	0.509375	0.45722	0.132941	39.46035	73.67742	23.96774	40.76871	52.51941
70.8291	0.914385	0.802243	0.373484	49.71364	158.4583	36.66667	76.55338	124.1604
78.69576	0.860534	0.815309	0.393996	57.63713	175.9474	36.36842	83.23064	142.1368
84.42998	0.884165	0.797888	0.418051	55.88178	182.6111	35.83333	90.41846	157.2222
72.22821	0.709623	0.62716	0.278915	50.43154	145.3415	38.14634	78.30248	115.8244
66.55779	0.764299	0.804241	0.293107	46.44698	143.1765	36.35294	71.55754	111.4235
77.58004	0.860268	0.781408	0.383991	51.53963	180.7297	36.45946	81.92163	138.818
71.87774	0.844446	0.749979	0.342618	39.83341	145.2917	36.33333	77.14144	120.675
72.88987	0.808182	0.694356	0.339763	50.99587	149.0714	37.64286	77.44022	122.3708
78.02244	0.839266	0.737739	0.372039	53.0018	165.3684	36.44737	84.57929	137.3912
71.88371	0.844672	0.678969	0.356921	50.27529	158.8478	36.67391	78.13746	123.058
76.13945	0.856535	0.759561	0.384044	50.12227	161.8889	37.44444	82.58621	133.8519
56.41859	0.765646	0.679974	0.310682	67.15855	123.2105	29.47368	59.0108	94.50526
66.98039	0.812067	0.687917	0.308258	55.41688	132.5625	37.0625	71.13643	107.2543
63.96537	0.736689	0.62716	0.232571	49.98955	128.1	37.25	67.18809	97.53
71.03749	0.87257	0.79291	0.3477	41.7997	142.5357	36.67857	74.58201	118.55
66.83497	0.74884	0.711257	0.282051	52.4839	134.9773	37.15909	70.30052	105.3011
70.32712	0.851221	0.713998	0.336057	52.1674	149.9231	36.80769	74.32952	119.659
67.0414	0.697975	0.598653	0.230568	71.03733	140.6818	37.13636	70.36294	104.6686
71.50935	0.866464	0.79179	0.347735	48.38971	146.875	36.875	75.0855	120.9958
75.00909	0.905874	0.749606	0.401775	63.79197	156.1429	36.71429	81.56715	127.3016
75.35177	0.823102	0.737541	0.378819	63.74429	162.12	36.84	83.66016	132.4453
69.72876	0.76862	0.658519	0.317408	61.22553	145.2727	36.86364	74.06493	114.1333
76.08163	0.87035	0.772398	0.364241	60.2645	168.3158	36.94737	80.10769	132.0421
76.22672	0.860323	0.766754	0.406871	62.1376	169.3871	36.16129	83.45454	137.643
82.33488	0.899605	0.80793	0.421313	52.6155	182	36.76471	88.57137	152.5882
75.69822	0.921547	0.870646	0.427964	48.50617	164.1765	36.23529	81.5206	134.9373
76.64832	0.916976	0.776111	0.412311	56.89085	167	36.375	83.75545	137.2417
73.60333	0.82941	0.715881	0.359937	59.03951	156.8293	36.36585	79.75578	126.8537
79.27882	0.925204	0.822687	0.43645	45.40843	176.1176	36.23529	85.80036	145.9176
74.01842	0.883438	0.792203	0.393586	62.71213	174.4737	36.68421	79.74718	132.9789
73.24202	0.864133	0.733778	0.383654	56.70896	159.2	36.55	79.30358	128.35
82.71351	0.881229	0.758864	0.40656	51.26812	187.425	36.3	89.60272	151.9883

RF_Swing_	RF_SwingS	RF_StrideL	RF_StepCy	RF_DutyCy	RF_ToeSpr	RF_Interm	RF_Manual	RF_PawAn
0.166232	45.62024	6.420779	0.358138	48.59379	-	-	-	-
0.115239	79.15808	6.628831	0.274547	54.36606	-	-	-	-
0.135038	43.18135	3.786494	0.316195	56.00669	-	-	-	-
0.140104	42.6403	5.279751	0.383509	62.89297	-	-	-	-
0.114094	59.38634	6.470224	0.278075	58.32628	-	-	-	-
0.150602	46.21057	6.597891	0.335196	54.95922	-	-	-	-
0.17404	28.63425	4.664567	0.537639	62.56051	-	-	-	-
0.163333	45.65113	6.769927	0.394432	57.35856	-	-	-	-
0.140288	43.39342	5.522306	0.371275	60.07479	-	-	-	-
0.163452	42.70466	5.134529	0.474436	56.85463	-	-	-	-
0.135041	42.69793	5.635065	0.370186	61.52019	-	-	-	-
0.138434	46.76227	5.305332	0.458866	62.45142	-	-	-	-
0.124865	46.6409	5.456342	0.348924	57.16003	-	-	-	-
0.115905	59.2474	6.732947	0.223149	47.94287	-	-	-	-
0.171321	36.35955	6.176841	0.422359	58.47563	-	-	-	-
0.114819	54.15941	6.165516	0.241093	50.96924	-	-	-	-
0.142116	45.64121	6.148047	0.285441	48.53094	-	-	-	-
0.10584	66.79317	6.944331	0.230723	53.61659	-	-	-	-
0.095826	53.79234	5.055321	0.410794	57.84388	-	-	-	-
0.089302	74.17536	6.346038	0.220216	54.64514	-	-	-	-
0.190662	30.14946	5.302973	0.516784	57.24356	-	-	-	-
0.133482	56.63604	7.492422	0.269249	50.4666	-	-	-	-
0.127607	46.15919	5.688953	0.352276	60.19309	-	-	-	-
0.224763	40.60659	4.967938	0.4613	60.9192	-	-	-	-
0.125457	51.14885	5.6576	0.270327	54.80499	-	-	-	-
0.126113	52.96087	6.530397	0.259717	51.46601	-	-	-	-
0.155794	46.59538	6.86117	0.470866	59.11389	-	-	-	-
0.156892	50.05696	7.562149	0.314487	50.31881	-	-	-	-
0.138165	56.52413	7.23605	0.309773	54.39583	-	-	-	-
0.138897	53.64057	7.329648	0.306268	53.74096	-	-	-	-
0.176511	37.05663	4.796046	0.409612	54.90442	-	-	-	-
0.153458	46.4602	6.946684	0.329078	52.15023	-	-	-	-
0.118532	56.54279	6.62649	0.25578	53.50372	-	-	-	-
0.169599	35.08168	5.905608	0.349175	51.15694	-	-	-	-
0.17745	34.10837	4.897746	0.484487	58.68889	-	-	-	-

RF_PawAnç	RF_SingleS	RF_InitialD	RF_Termin	RF_BodySp	RF_BodySp	RH_Stand_	RH_Standlr	RH_MaxCo
-	0.141548	0.057497	0.01473	21.75353	36.3093	0.209487	-10.7537	38.56349
-	0.114827	0.029176	0.009969	27.5855	70.09325	0.265465	-9.21615	32.22497
-	0.081561	0.045581	0.055226	13.92421	40.53512	0.111005	-4.44138	24.42158
-	0.092318	0.06503	0.076597	14.5398	26.62718	0.232896	-5.74468	25.90786
-	0.123027	0.029268	0.014634	23.59924	10.64388	0.170128	-8.73586	24.86749
-	0.135888	0.016663	0.025335	20.19495	10.44693	0.197106	-7.69508	26.66343
-	0.149165	0.085531	0.119056	10.9654	69.6301	0.354198	-7.03188	34.95339
-	0.158526	0.033081	0.045563	18.54138	15.44009	0.206369	-8.61838	37.10762
-	0.130004	0.02865	0.077855	16.46535	38.35929	0.222277	-7.77381	26.79737
-	0.145964	0.099018	0.083	17.43996	57.39748	0.309593	-7.98199	29.05819
-	0.151617	0.054217	0.031889	15.68446	37.2985	0.232625	-6.61487	27.05416
-	0.116059	0.122734	0.081327	17.79869	58.6157	0.32156	-7.96517	30.92099
-	0.125849	0.040428	0.032621	20.08143	46.9622	0.190466	-9.41796	33.27403
-	0.099923	0.007492	0.002498	28.87689	12.87022	0.13156	-13.3619	28.64615
-	0.163942	0.031007	0.035991	14.52629	16.9451	0.142623	-8.7666	35.84229
-	0.110731	0.015665	0.004631	24.77257	14.0618	0.138098	-11.1223	26.68887
-	0.129177	0.006249	0.009372	22.94362	25.02763	0.137893	-11.6081	28.23048
-	0.10066	0.014281	0.009536	29.75057	20.70085	0.149638	-11.891	30.65368
-	0.062909	0.097786	0.202831	25.53222	187.4296	0.428357	-16.7009	31.68111
-	0.083106	0.005222	0.045004	31.60973	49.21565	0.160536	-13.0992	29.61471
-	0.189589	0.072331	0.058373	12.06938	47.30083	0.293246	-5.41154	29.57297
-	0.13107	0.002136	0.002138	26.77313	6.573898	0.084984	-10.8318	26.10201
-	0.14686	0.021146	0.067522	17.84517	31.63894	0.170074	-7.99425	28.63233
-	0.134127	0.050754	0.04259	14.12983	51.54012	0.23235	-7.52139	28.12372
-	0.108041	0.005542	0.033207	21.03581	18.24222	0.133367	-9.27428	28.95429
-	0.120489	0.004996	0.008119	24.74406	7.498845	0.116194	-10.4113	31.80812
-	0.191272	0.112859	0.016143	16.71628	46.53892	0.246444	-7.63694	27.81512
-	0.13619	0.039193	0.011408	22.05755	37.60772	0.250784	-7.85207	22.17945
-	0.138823	0.016864	0.026052	25.14924	13.12327	0.151435	-10.0624	26.47095
-	0.145063	0.015381	0.006921	24.58048	14.51613	0.152445	-8.52529	22.25889
-	0.102599	0.103409	0.049956	14.97939	55.18738	0.298583	-6.39158	22.96624
-	0.150576	0.010002	0.013987	21.86931	14.47374	0.138911	-9.57332	37.29837
-	0.119084	0.007844	0.011408	25.09703	7.182955	0.16286	-9.42725	31.70887
-	0.153758	0.00704	0.019366	16.11701	14.41547	0.157955	-6.46195	22.69794
-	0.135714	0.119635	0.052887	13.42511	45.54068	0.331759	-6.43627	27.31531

RH_MaxCo	RH_MaxCo	RH_MaxCo	RH_PrintLe	RH_PrintW	RH_PrintA	RH_MaxInt	RH_MaxInt	RH_MinInt
0.206374	123.8966	65.12958	0.679559	0.646624	0.241733	46.70595	126.7931	37.75862
0.186173	116.8889	63.31798	0.695934	0.637613	0.232419	42.80573	122.1111	38.36111
0.043391	42.96774	32.72716	0.316855	0.352019	0.055088	39.9955	46.03226	25.35484
0.309433	163.4091	70.94348	0.932517	0.909383	0.387943	35.44095	168.5	37.04545
0.340506	174.7222	78.32684	0.92561	0.829246	0.410253	37.81473	179.5556	36.33333
0.347437	193.3889	82.2053	0.908341	0.839698	0.427365	46.21419	198.4444	36.11111
0.14374	140.1778	74.58392	0.558129	0.540752	0.173112	35.09802	146.1333	41.24444
0.189376	132.619	71.24569	0.618718	0.689877	0.231707	40.6334	140	40.7619
0.321511	182.4615	85.59453	0.830498	0.739728	0.387293	39.76042	187.7179	38.17949
0.216529	152.6786	74.54383	0.721591	0.64284	0.265684	38.14177	158.1071	38.21429
0.283192	159.4	74.23243	0.835121	0.740049	0.343625	31.36678	164.9	37.9
0.23321	155	77.72873	0.803845	0.619868	0.287885	41.82733	161.9535	38.4186
0.341514	177.1224	76.98428	0.895724	0.883144	0.409785	36.55928	181.8776	37.4898
0.363899	182.2778	77.85573	0.908341	0.766529	0.431047	33.4347	188.4444	36.88889
0.074752	78.37931	50.08665	0.493055	0.367646	0.106078	37.64057	83.13793	31.7931
0.302166	160.2353	74.53037	0.808182	0.771038	0.335193	40.25312	164.5294	37.70588
0.174337	124.6667	64.6515	0.674965	0.671958	0.203672	34.04232	127	37.14286
0.269805	173.92	73.99472	0.855429	0.883042	0.329537	37.17491	178.24	36.44
0.225358	163.0857	80.79112	0.744238	0.697044	0.271588	34.05304	166.4857	38.4
0.278912	168.2857	77.20598	0.799301	0.739153	0.343662	31.61728	172.9286	37.53571
0.156707	95.15385	58.03904	0.681455	0.576505	0.212641	51.03693	104.1154	38.19231
0.184097	148.3478	75.09447	0.627084	0.62716	0.220882	31.09871	151.5652	41.86957
0.255639	156.9333	76.31673	0.721147	0.746321	0.292029	36.77287	162.9667	39.5
0.189997	120.0769	65.697	0.925344	0.759829	0.239784	61.03012	150.5769	39.88462
0.23361	169.4167	82.74013	0.743424	0.687263	0.272924	43.75976	175.6667	41.54167
0.226343	164.3158	79.79318	0.742742	0.617258	0.260612	45.91222	168.2632	37.68421
0.240307	174.4146	87.19131	0.774823	0.651635	0.294321	35.70355	184.8049	41.07317
0.358242	177.3529	81.77036	0.925204	0.80793	0.417643	39.44454	182.0588	38.70588
0.340691	171.7143	78.31145	0.808182	0.815309	0.383765	36.26606	176.2381	38.7619
0.389459	184.5	80.05619	0.894526	0.87454	0.442961	35.79129	192.7778	38.66667
0.324585	172.8409	85.34971	0.851982	0.739764	0.387765	37.61893	179.4545	40.81818
0.349148	186.05	89.98421	0.823724	0.793358	0.404903	32.6076	191.25	39.4
0.290777	153.0526	74.89889	1.086301	0.749292	0.431344	47.99958	161.2632	36.94737
0.247711	157.1667	77.55076	0.675557	0.658519	0.293719	31.99296	165.6667	41.13333
0.374628	190.0213	88.33351	0.869027	0.811305	0.435103	35.48279	196.0851	39.65957

RH_MeanI	RH_MeanI	RH_Swing	RH_SwingS	RH_StrideL	RH_StepCy	RH_DutyCy	RH_ToeSpr	RH_Interm
69.40153	101.4421	0.128461	45.92575	5.541507	0.350721	58.45092	-	-
66.8183	97.494	0.107269	48.29385	5.287256	0.393333	57.57868	-	-
34.90214	37.039	0.172389	27.11761	3.848177	0.285666	46.0004	-	-
76.52783	134.4606	0.135357	39.18365	5.316268	0.373025	59.26567	-	-
84.5728	146.1	0.096417	67.74053	6.452067	0.262671	62.36523	-	-
91.05549	168.3963	0.123231	56.06129	6.720091	0.321781	60.91659	-	-
80.63722	111.828	0.125744	29.96354	4.085648	0.49209	55.8238	-	-
78.87093	113.7702	0.121492	43.84672	5.23451	0.313437	57.04967	-	-
93.32926	154.6601	0.111204	43.95264	4.810615	0.333894	61.27788	-	-
78.51878	123.6476	0.11876	47.1552	4.361172	0.407538	60.98756	-	-
79.56098	132.2175	0.112423	42.83751	5.114427	0.345919	61.36455	-	-
82.11368	127.1018	0.107866	41.23792	4.559267	0.411616	58.37471	-	-
81.7496	143.0567	0.085552	54.85749	4.759257	0.280569	61.99229	-	-
84.76558	153.4481	0.095922	69.87592	6.649869	0.225815	57.32914	-	-
51.62013	64.62019	0.136495	28.84707	4.007053	0.259576	49.3866	-	-
79.42616	131.3216	0.097954	60.76818	5.859568	0.236143	56.95533	-	-
66.58931	98.4119	0.12812	48.46154	5.755998	0.267364	51.3185	-	-
80.6502	137.048	0.100276	76.75534	7.638951	0.251898	57.72007	-	-
85.15629	135.3337	0.082144	70.73747	6.058894	0.564598	54.50905	-	-
82.08116	137.681	0.072307	78.73193	5.778365	0.210997	57.72452	-	-
63.60549	83.32862	0.185262	26.01885	4.769587	0.462494	52.51511	-	-
78.28997	118.0066	0.095715	43.44137	4.84015	0.173495	43.98596	-	-
81.09629	127.2408	0.094691	37.36573	3.98787	0.264429	55.47909	-	-
72.41174	113.3359	0.198523	34.60313	4.559147	0.439075	56.7874	-	-
87.76171	139.2979	0.100225	42.08519	4.813091	0.233169	51.80602	-	-
83.906	131.2596	0.14234	46.40138	6.533985	0.259717	44.62414	-	-
94.07883	149.4813	0.109822	41.22982	4.693703	0.364151	60.65427	-	-
88.22312	153.1157	0.117668	54.1795	6.716414	0.32941	58.99817	-	-
84.77989	142.6138	0.10026	53.31294	5.634448	0.245359	56.80073	-	-
88.66236	158.5889	0.111079	53.8147	6.338239	0.264097	55.93296	-	-
91.49128	147.2339	0.112444	42.67509	4.487739	0.416266	60.46737	-	-
96.37506	160.2117	0.132857	43.3249	5.680136	0.270417	51.86974	-	-
77.53948	133.014	0.096074	70.86146	6.571024	0.255156	62.52916	-	-
83.48763	128.3479	0.091642	34.51289	3.828767	0.242393	56.12747	-	-
95.20292	163.7902	0.098047	40.81267	4.109974	0.414976	66.36805	-	-

RH_Manua	RH_PawAn	RH_PawAn	RH_SingleS	RH_InitialD	RH_Termin	RH_BodySp	RH_BodySp	LF_Stand_(:
-	-	-	0.138346	0.023857	0.071585	19.68106	33.84019	0.204892
-	-	-	0.096389	0.015122	0.086727	21.87339	65.34539	0.167074
-	-	-	0.115793	0.005205	0.003038	13.32597	44.26714	0.285325
-	-	-	0.120649	0.077632	0.038838	14.56401	21.93713	0.185731
-	-	-	0.107368	0.03756	0.028751	24.03764	11.79481	0.154072
-	-	-	0.117237	0.046649	0.036664	20.84393	10.47784	0.183788
-	-	-	0.132409	0.147396	0.044314	12.7533	62.00851	0.412745
-	-	-	0.109839	0.051932	0.042443	16.75113	17.04541	0.229196
-	-	-	0.076382	0.070946	0.077827	15.71579	34.74263	0.261781
-	-	-	0.086207	0.084169	0.132053	16.68018	87.29509	0.243074
-	-	-	0.1193	0.031828	0.086213	16.30691	27.60851	0.208072
-	-	-	0.112531	0.152995	0.068566	16.96185	58.6028	0.305095
-	-	-	0.102863	0.030626	0.066428	19.62354	41.93604	0.177988
-	-	-	0.101169	0.019985	0.011866	27.91624	14.34392	0.11517
-	-	-	0.122546	0.011436	0.00849	14.81161	17.35867	0.246444
-	-	-	0.100354	0.014619	0.026594	24.00698	17.92604	0.12296
-	-	-	0.124803	0.004371	0.027479	22.44072	21.43263	0.13664
-	-	-	0.107961	0.026271	0.018606	30.4062	18.18757	0.125618
-	-	-	0.070982	0.004598	0.284899	33.21746	192.8118	0.445739
-	-	-	0.074553	0.013301	0.060191	31.86755	40.19304	0.149018
-	-	-	0.164656	0.0928	0.047389	11.06155	43.72735	0.299359
-	-	-	0.071933	0.005771	0.006306	26.25799	9.485044	0.127303
-	-	-	0.083214	0.024787	0.065435	17.36271	31.29968	0.217761
-	-	-	0.129591	0.037026	0.049366	13.48096	51.46687	0.23318
-	-	-	0.088325	0.037471	0.008077	22.00903	16.29694	0.178935
-	-	-	0.097225	0.011984	0.009994	24.69553	6.474099	0.13512
-	-	-	0.09928	0.030886	0.072954	16.48729	50.03289	0.235109
-	-	-	0.110441	0.057999	0.089288	22.00367	39.53731	0.197285
-	-	-	0.089747	0.032826	0.027544	22.73755	15.48221	0.176954
-	-	-	0.108399	0.029321	0.013969	23.66871	13.77765	0.155914
-	-	-	0.096842	0.118804	0.070214	16.27338	62.93303	0.260826
-	-	-	0.107703	0.01388	0.016103	21.90123	16.94054	0.167659
-	-	-	0.103149	0.01863	0.040584	24.65363	6.532613	0.136823
-	-	-	0.077963	0.020689	0.056153	15.94378	17.41691	0.197033
-	-	-	0.093404	0.118758	0.108368	13.35993	47.23149	0.315345

LF_StandIn	LF_MaxCor	LF_MaxCor	LF_MaxCor	LF_MaxCor	LF_PrintLe	LF_PrintWi	LF_PrintAr	LF_MaxInte
-7.20939	49.11868	0.206493	113.2692	64.29079	0.738841	0.574093	0.257179	61.50954
-9.26079	43.79675	0.243293	121.7667	63.20241	0.783315	0.660609	0.29047	54.07155
-4.65549	51.59053	0.139853	66.56522	36.27391	0.689252	0.594439	0.197828	51.5428
-2.40034	30.91668	0.213011	126.2	64.76151	0.648618	0.576988	0.2546	41.24746
-5.88879	31.54823	0.33639	162.1667	78.64754	0.877257	0.770014	0.394874	48.66399
-3.66506	28.99195	0.322961	160.2222	78.84016	0.887618	0.815309	0.391842	69.34437
-3.07656	38.73204	0.246332	141.1282	68.61924	0.747608	0.741336	0.315413	47.32831
-3.27247	33.24334	0.202001	126.0952	65.606	0.677925	0.683904	0.259928	41.47011
-3.09827	27.83266	0.358346	174.6061	83.23259	0.881653	0.803906	0.407142	55.07254
-4.77146	26.89146	0.282873	143.2414	73.85483	0.771739	0.687714	0.328316	44.24386
-4.92254	37.45064	0.286831	139.5667	71.90122	0.789531	0.721235	0.338296	47.994
-3.38107	35.20186	0.289186	156.9024	76.39716	0.796052	0.680699	0.341964	54.03448
-6.91299	40.38475	0.301212	152.2553	74.56668	0.785696	0.669861	0.33846	57.6486
-7.93973	29.2811	0.347004	153.0526	76.74956	0.857262	0.775699	0.39256	40.08965
-2.62744	43.85489	0.217453	109.5	52.80238	0.729059	0.635713	0.275406	58.22039
-7.80398	39.16206	0.263	138.2121	68.75516	0.770504	0.642364	0.30258	56.17154
-8.81615	44.07528	0.191663	129.8421	64.38174	0.752558	0.610656	0.237629	56.4085
-9.17836	42.12163	0.296029	151.6296	73.99346	0.863442	0.79208	0.360434	56.81108
-8.94445	33.83222	0.26269	133.5	68.29413	0.812067	0.764352	0.319224	49.10217
-10.6614	40.52667	0.290824	146.6364	70.56164	0.87035	0.783951	0.358169	55.92872
-3.76355	39.84309	0.189521	128.5652	67.98016	0.654114	0.635341	0.233935	60.64771
-6.30459	35.81093	0.26742	142.8824	72.40346	0.863036	0.726768	0.331638	61.43474
-4.1544	36.87095	0.307643	148.6667	76.16072	0.831865	0.710782	0.363899	60.54556
-3.44558	38.41915	0.283265	158.6087	74.73949	0.791964	0.708964	0.358362	57.57071
-4.86761	40.00853	0.335102	159.1579	75.52823	0.85399	0.719584	0.374502	61.9404
-8.24938	46.73527	0.262869	143.1579	71.83204	0.795094	0.673372	0.307399	64.59506
-3.64251	39.00168	0.266686	147.7143	72.14267	0.804629	0.745425	0.336533	55.48729
-4.7644	33.87968	0.334848	154.0588	79.49268	0.910576	0.800552	0.415579	53.39086
-5.38223	39.25685	0.347248	159.375	77.2038	0.909205	0.815309	0.415966	55.37227
-4.06809	32.71258	0.322392	164.1875	78.27229	0.901434	0.780031	0.400127	58.06886
-4.06562	35.13995	0.246819	141.1304	69.95792	0.773043	0.704874	0.309625	48.76075
-3.54074	34.3731	0.310614	149.6111	76.25712	1.005047	0.867572	0.438629	38.4718
-7.85617	44.95118	0.351591	151.8235	76.95983	0.884977	0.723079	0.40113	66.23959
-3.09592	35.72407	0.315033	150.9	72.89214	0.923192	0.840395	0.385018	61.43498
-3.29271	35.68121	0.364322	175.5581	85.7812	0.893482	0.777387	0.422534	46.56112

LF_MaxInt	LF_MinInt	LF_MeanIn	LF_MeanIn	LF_Swing_	LF_SwingS	LF_StrideL	LF_StepCyc	LF_DutyCyc
119.1154	37.46154	67.94775	98.05385	0.148714	46.09212	6.129763	0.349601	53.13315
127.8	37.4	66.44206	98.11194	0.146134	54.584	6.852907	0.298656	48.83793
71	23.04348	38.7711	53.38599	0.149578	54.68395	5.291847	0.442272	64.54576
136.8	37.73333	69.23167	104.5339	0.088201	58.56262	3.775376	0.275061	63.56976
170.9444	36.83333	83.94937	140.5926	0.123691	53.73063	6.394084	0.280648	54.94408
178.5556	36.66667	84.10055	141.3185	0.135888	49.75784	6.556576	0.324454	57.20926
150.2051	36.46154	74.60266	117.3282	0.174323	32.4664	5.445727	0.620527	62.75207
129.2381	37.14286	68.9027	101.5508	0.147565	42.61718	5.96183	0.36836	59.84338
190.3333	36.33333	90.4626	156.1172	0.143933	44.26105	5.989129	0.408282	60.52119
152.4138	37.17241	79.35443	122.7626	0.126368	40.65184	4.206547	0.378347	58.89254
144.4	36.73333	76.54283	121.3378	0.14617	40.55761	5.537815	0.355948	57.20043
167.9512	36.65854	83.31161	135.5878	0.10722	53.16729	4.874907	0.409245	64.60852
165	36.87234	80.71355	129.8199	0.138099	45.90409	4.952803	0.319275	57.72874
158.3158	36.68421	82.3613	134.5579	0.108666	62.8793	6.686564	0.219827	50.60435
117.7273	28.86364	56.50994	89.0697	0.155314	40.36963	5.804036	0.37776	57.82737
143.5455	37.0303	71.65499	111.3672	0.120338	51.77322	6.123648	0.244607	49.49328
134.0526	37.31579	66.14211	98.63509	0.142268	46.18944	6.056779	0.283942	48.62847
160.6296	36.81481	78.99119	131.3358	0.112491	68.80837	7.348702	0.239437	51.24485
141.2813	36.78125	72.84561	113.3323	0.096458	78.09913	6.119502	0.607743	58.43749
151.4545	36.77273	73.34107	121.5	0.099726	72.82353	7.153768	0.256925	52.50793
143.087	37.21739	71.43025	105.5749	0.194578	29.74402	5.26492	0.507905	57.60828
154.5882	37.35294	74.7305	117.3059	0.141047	53.28762	7.443778	0.267849	47.23214
160.1905	36.95238	81.552	128.3746	0.143691	39.72673	5.559614	0.362243	56.53095
168.7391	37	80.16637	132.7607	0.14754	38.07426	5.516514	0.382301	58.11364
171.1579	36.47368	82.29917	134.3298	0.123416	51.74539	6.313977	0.306601	56.78737
149.9474	37.05263	74.80009	116.0316	0.12361	52.98361	6.500774	0.258469	51.87148
156.6286	36.62857	77.03047	122.3374	0.175097	40.03781	6.000803	0.41777	56.02068
164.2353	37.11765	85.10575	140.251	0.139756	53.74851	7.455885	0.337954	55.7861
169.3125	36.8125	83.42809	138.2083	0.139589	57.25846	7.2483	0.312894	54.06714
175.8125	36.875	83.42047	141.1833	0.147361	51.93969	7.35073	0.307026	52.02999
149.5	37.08696	75.4626	117.729	0.129638	49.88595	4.470861	0.391937	61.01678
157.0556	36.72222	82.50196	134.0815	0.154572	48.73698	7.037874	0.327114	53.17848
163.0588	37.29412	83.39642	132.9608	0.119084	56.68792	6.662812	0.255993	53.47846
164.6	36.8	77.37078	127.78	0.156106	39.62618	6.028439	0.348591	55.33554
182.7674	36.25581	91.70526	154.6729	0.128571	38.49336	4.758974	0.450744	64.90658

LF_ToeSpr	LF_Interme	LF_Manual	LF_PawAnξ	LF_PawAnξ	LF_SingleSt	LF_InitialD	LF_Termin:	LF_BodySp
-	-	-	-	-	0.14145	0.010431	0.053976	21.05493
-	-	-	-	-	0.10733	0.009965	0.035762	26.54262
-	-	-	-	-	0.156936	0.05092	0.096063	13.52341
-	-	-	-	-	0.091448	0.03163	0.062534	14.25412
-	-	-	-	-	0.112848	0.014343	0.02744	23.21013
-	-	-	-	-	0.150602	0.026673	0.016666	20.77377
-	-	-	-	-	0.199542	0.14689	0.109542	12.42428
-	-	-	-	-	0.16262	0.039944	0.0321	17.22606
-	-	-	-	-	0.1548	0.076692	0.029593	16.45686
-	-	-	-	-	0.11219	0.055557	0.07594	15.40831
-	-	-	-	-	0.12924	0.031092	0.053814	15.62518
-	-	-	-	-	0.126066	0.074551	0.122765	17.36022
-	-	-	-	-	0.110798	0.02811	0.04101	18.76637
-	-	-	-	-	0.105914	0.001998	0.007991	28.68824
-	-	-	-	-	0.161243	0.034586	0.030484	15.02955
-	-	-	-	-	0.10375	0.004803	0.015507	24.26654
-	-	-	-	-	0.126861	0.008821	0.005881	23.23975
-	-	-	-	-	0.104305	0.009969	0.014931	31.24434
-	-	-	-	-	0.108064	0.24373	0.117343	31.05802
-	-	-	-	-	0.100255	0.049741	0.005772	32.774
-	-	-	-	-	0.18646	0.060395	0.075613	11.90125
-	-	-	-	-	0.125038	0.003836	0.0023	26.73561
-	-	-	-	-	0.120366	0.058838	0.035731	16.90849
-	-	-	-	-	0.135885	0.046692	0.056144	14.60214
-	-	-	-	-	0.139041	0.036924	0.007629	21.85375
-	-	-	-	-	0.123616	0.008119	0.004371	24.66004
-	-	-	-	-	0.129143	0.015158	0.100836	15.64887
-	-	-	-	-	0.153327	0.011409	0.039195	22.35651
-	-	-	-	-	0.136031	0.021346	0.015659	25.36283
-	-	-	-	-	0.137364	0.006921	0.015381	24.10425
-	-	-	-	-	0.127367	0.034717	0.105897	15.8075
-	-	-	-	-	0.149177	0.014986	0.010001	21.74019
-	-	-	-	-	0.118532	0.011228	0.00811	25.21433
-	-	-	-	-	0.16725	0.019366	0.009386	16.27882
-	-	-	-	-	0.164359	0.049566	0.1129	13.15208

LF_BodySp	LH_Stand_	LH_StandIn	LH_MaxCo	LH_MaxCo	LH_MaxCo	LH_MaxCo	LH_PrintLe	LH_PrintW
41.2256	0.192977	-8.74461	33.42253	0.148562	110.6552	65.07509	0.662409	0.501728
69.70013	0.214787	-9.39739	27.80194	0.241733	125.3429	65.21727	0.71049	0.707795
35.06917	0.110984	-5.99146	24.2886	0.050524	40.95833	31.76236	0.39632	0.32142
23.86976	0.19614	-6.86501	22.3121	0.228505	140.1071	69.44976	0.71715	0.736914
9.610069	0.156275	-10.5394	28.9104	0.261042	173.4286	80.75825	0.858508	0.615215
9.757044	0.195152	-6.80874	20.96367	0.34803	186.8947	80.59126	0.906342	0.841715
67.27716	0.284695	-5.96153	33.85169	0.149901	126.3404	71.25876	0.621678	0.637836
26.10682	0.243669	-7.34254	40.37996	0.165899	123.3	66.11773	0.671413	0.677333
37.6313	0.280419	-5.51698	27.09841	0.368231	186.1111	81.31338	0.996412	0.86583
62.74348	0.341788	-7.4945	34.68592	0.251841	162.7037	76.24155	0.762132	0.722396
42.938	0.228009	-7.55091	44.95497	0.204563	147.2333	72.86574	0.685918	0.681514
65.99382	0.234724	-8.83343	24.29063	0.185022	152.3636	82.8693	0.614896	0.54734
49.04702	0.189919	-11.9381	35.33166	0.291887	132.2045	71.97403	0.843504	0.662795
13.92273	0.126743	-14.3298	30.27331	0.385172	180.8421	80.23482	0.880166	0.878025
15.81558	0.129892	-9.75631	35.82139	0.081626	82.83871	52.44987	0.495337	0.461266
13.33707	0.123303	-12.8795	27.34133	0.249121	157	76.47364	0.705114	0.74104
22.49691	0.124584	-12.8488	35.70246	0.134606	130.5714	67.17099	0.630559	0.606255
21.46051	0.130408	-11.8501	23.66747	0.254102	166.8966	74.71684	0.791032	0.823959
191.8928	0.532243	-13.4444	25.02678	0.309268	176.75	74.87849	0.901434	0.822028
43.76357	0.193425	-11.5083	23.25164	0.330699	179.1818	77.38604	0.921214	0.803906
43.97401	0.290632	-6.01923	31.00987	0.178701	101.7917	59.50011	0.774508	0.629774
7.272037	0.154599	-9.85406	27.61992	0.258791	164.875	74.23848	0.87035	0.693796
31.68987	0.238345	-7.6951	30.74263	0.259193	168.4783	78.08381	0.891973	0.837123
40.95844	0.240197	-7.71739	40.60804	0.200145	123.2381	63.53181	1.009487	0.74662
18.42183	0.15635	-8.7085	27.46223	0.30004	181.0909	80.94416	0.861872	0.755443
5.974976	0.114364	-12.0334	28.59987	0.223408	165.55	78.46697	0.752231	0.705556
49.73203	0.255414	-6.06784	29.21514	0.294574	170.2632	85.68665	0.80491	0.719584
38.85427	0.253826	-7.91002	29.36675	0.325457	158.5263	73.68799	0.929245	0.818609
11.58497	0.203738	-8.64633	19.56488	0.43741	184.6875	81.0757	0.983029	0.909383
12.23421	0.164013	-9.50204	25.57048	0.388674	193.375	81.15002	0.882006	0.834907
60.59843	0.29884	-6.49308	32.12534	0.271365	167.4667	76.5289	0.787459	0.70242
15.94578	0.175676	-8.23221	19.22871	0.438936	177.2105	81.1293	1.109205	0.887927
6.136538	0.129286	-9.03533	19.09004	0.304301	149.0476	73.65169	0.899953	0.791417
18.32868	0.243224	-6.10318	33.36618	0.326024	150.5238	70.27657	0.926597	0.8392
49.80134	0.344176	-6.16607	24.06264	0.331674	178.8409	81.88196	0.877414	0.801055

LH_PrintAr	LH_MaxInt	LH_MaxInt	LH_MinInt	LH_MeanI	LH_MeanI	LH_Swing	LH_SwingS	LH_StrideL
0.184728	44.71804	116.6207	41.58621	69.73693	94.06347	0.132864	41.57425	5.194057
0.291528	42.89594	131.5143	38.88571	70.40996	106.9301	0.096838	60.05001	5.795206
0.069531	42.59882	46.375	25.125	33.92867	36.97818	0.233368	21.20204	4.622714
0.2849	30.29423	143.75	39.53571	74.8247	116.2342	0.095514	39.34555	4.115057
0.318226	32.49642	176.7143	37.57143	85.66899	138.7513	0.101403	57.77989	5.936322
0.419031	39.76911	192.7895	36.21053	87.53975	159.4807	0.114914	57.15752	6.412941
0.185904	47.96223	137.7234	40.12766	78.40863	108.4833	0.137783	34.4755	4.351057
0.208787	44.70149	129.6	38.05	72.15132	102.6917	0.140379	46.04662	6.21192
0.460181	42.25989	194.6111	36.19444	90.17505	163.7253	0.089136	61.9806	5.300977
0.305127	41.7727	166.4444	37.22222	80.74574	131.0449	0.090779	47.29304	4.379131
0.262787	36.6001	154.3	39.13333	77.70975	119.5424	0.128898	41.11967	5.358686
0.228051	29.69527	157.6364	45.67273	86.49372	123.3129	0.100332	35.9171	3.48252
0.336725	61.33492	144.7045	38.81818	77.18083	118.4063	0.113868	46.00142	5.173218
0.441604	30.70871	183.6842	36.89474	85.81741	152.9649	0.101169	65.95932	6.592803
0.108918	29.14755	90.09677	35.12903	55.47434	67.72131	0.139535	26.7088	3.744676
0.277952	30.31798	160.4737	38.63158	82.07261	128.4198	0.096666	52.35322	5.36829
0.162826	36.10896	134.7619	37.42857	69.71053	97.90159	0.126463	45.16681	5.382766
0.308553	37.00774	174.7931	36.89655	80.07815	134.8713	0.103117	68.54815	6.998224
0.380563	36.12001	185.25	36.5	80.27877	140.719	0.087618	82.72159	6.971337
0.397513	39.64987	185.2273	36.95455	84.77554	150.6394	0.088086	82.68789	7.105879
0.234423	65.97413	119.1667	37.75	65.80381	90.55454	0.176771	28.61286	4.816753
0.306065	37.07786	171.3125	36.9375	79.6971	132.2625	0.114328	65.62696	7.399626
0.327001	47.13228	175.0435	38.13043	82.74388	139.8783	0.11883	47.59164	5.403395
0.267726	62.45221	139.4286	37.38095	68.57512	104.9608	0.156175	37.76554	5.762032
0.353916	41.29844	187.7273	39.95455	87.38666	148.1617	0.1013	50.65979	5.306982
0.261618	35.32998	167.9	38.8	83.07783	133.0144	0.113409	52.24011	5.738114
0.360445	31.56751	180.4737	41.63158	90.80218	144.6877	0.105933	41.94849	4.731649
0.395433	46.916	172.3158	37.31579	80.04705	138.5018	0.114182	55.39315	6.576852
0.498818	27.24944	189.1875	36.625	88.97431	157.9542	0.117361	65.67826	7.192715
0.435704	33.05918	195.375	36.6875	88.45243	160.4958	0.135082	56.48459	7.368799
0.318412	35.81292	173.1333	37.28889	83.23374	134.8122	0.095651	44.84001	4.290434
0.53169	33.98998	193.3158	36.73684	88.80614	159.4105	0.123662	51.65692	6.555171
0.383765	38.21838	157.5238	40.71429	79.28792	130.6429	0.092072	60.71783	5.766862
0.403074	53.80198	160.9524	36.52381	76.25921	128.8794	0.120269	49.42253	5.827235
0.385905	36.28045	186.0682	37.22727	89.6458	153.2265	0.100237	43.43025	4.361122

LH_StepCy	LH_DutyCy	LH_ToeSpr	LH_Interm	LH_Manual	LH_PawAn	LH_PawAn	LH_SingleS	LH_InitialD
0.331982	53.35471	-	-	-	-	-	0.117382	0.062174
0.264819	57.29938	-	-	-	-	-	0.109486	0.088757
0.348089	35.66163	-	-	-	-	-	0.107917	0.003176
0.289875	61.33038	-	-	-	-	-	0.102872	0.027129
0.253803	58.53474	-	-	-	-	-	0.090391	0.023073
0.321068	63.18544	-	-	-	-	-	0.115529	0.033123
0.440334	60.28007	-	-	-	-	-	0.105193	0.047862
0.402971	63.89393	-	-	-	-	-	0.155166	0.053772
0.373912	71.93459	-	-	-	-	-	0.121706	0.085807
0.411153	64.54856	-	-	-	-	-	0.114372	0.1184
0.355916	58.49996	-	-	-	-	-	0.108203	0.086976
0.340779	55.46222	-	-	-	-	-	0.07449	0.05456
0.311474	56.661	-	-	-	-	-	0.08873	0.068336
0.223574	54.36718	-	-	-	-	-	0.095922	0.009992
0.264131	50.17026	-	-	-	-	-	0.106696	0.008121
0.217806	54.99493	-	-	-	-	-	0.083478	0.024306
0.252395	49.6217	-	-	-	-	-	0.105392	0.023317
0.233251	54.41858	-	-	-	-	-	0.087085	0.017697
0.713004	58.7188	-	-	-	-	-	0.086339	0.473036
0.259143	59.10165	-	-	-	-	-	0.085271	0.064697
0.46852	56.77506	-	-	-	-	-	0.160966	0.042075
0.268546	57.51814	-	-	-	-	-	0.136528	0.007675
0.361471	62.91644	-	-	-	-	-	0.120841	0.085841
0.404283	59.63232	-	-	-	-	-	0.151749	0.057594
0.256613	57.12112	-	-	-	-	-	0.106572	0.008927
0.224452	49.73418	-	-	-	-	-	0.101549	0.008328
0.358285	55.35578	-	-	-	-	-	0.10412	0.118353
0.321319	60.62462	-	-	-	-	-	0.11553	0.0328
0.32286	61.75053	-	-	-	-	-	0.128905	0.032736
0.305493	54.82735	-	-	-	-	-	0.124323	0.017648
0.386145	70.70866	-	-	-	-	-	0.099656	0.060183
0.303549	57.44579	-	-	-	-	-	0.147909	0.018658
0.225732	57.50868	-	-	-	-	-	0.080905	0.030995
0.361904	65.74496	-	-	-	-	-	0.134137	0.078693
0.441519	69.9469	-	-	-	-	-	0.102701	0.108834

LH_Termin	LH_BodySp	LH_BodySpee	StepSeque	StepSeque	StepSeque	StepSeque	StepSeque	StepSeque
0.020719	19.53386	36.9657669	21	28.57143	14.28571	9.52381	42.85714	4.761905
0.046001	25.40879	62.4082036	24	16.66667	20.83333	25	37.5	0
0.005442	14.18907	37.2620151	16	6.25	18.75	6.25	56.25	12.5
0.059399	13.35062	31.0690065	16	25	12.5	12.5	50	0
0.038035	23.27765	11.6413506	16	6.25	31.25	6.25	56.25	0
0.039355	20.29071	12.6254793	15	20	33.33333	26.66667	20	0
0.136853	13.1262	67.8267434	27	18.51852	22.22222	11.11111	44.44444	0
0.064527	17.52425	16.0129809	16	6.25	25	0	62.5	6.25
0.082442	15.99896	33.8379633	28	46.42857	7.142857	7.142857	39.28571	0
0.118014	17.35374	69.4720109	19	26.31579	10.52632	15.78947	47.36842	0
0.035282	16.11636	23.1924162	22	9.090909	22.72727	4.545455	59.09091	4.545455
0.127589	17.35493	65.7127454	27	40.74074	7.407407	14.81481	29.62963	7.407407
0.032387	19.48505	44.7945421	37	32.43243	10.81081	8.108108	48.64865	0
0.021316	27.88966	14.1041384	16	12.5	75	6.25	6.25	0
0.012175	13.38038	24.3615329	16	12.5	6.25	0	62.5	0
0.015885	23.40695	13.7252615	30	20	23.33333	43.33333	6.666667	0
0.005551	23.50886	22.9427625	18	22.22222	22.22222	44.44444	11.11111	0
0.025362	29.739	19.1827488	22	22.72727	18.18182	45.45455	13.63636	0
0.005751	33.10999	187.907353	27	44.44444	11.11111	33.33333	7.407407	3.703704
0.052339	31.67286	40.0815211	21	14.28571	19.04762	61.90476	0	4.761905
0.093287	11.29042	48.951403	20	10	10	0	75	0
0.009198	26.4798	6.73403341	12	25	8.333333	41.66667	8.333333	8.333333
0.03496	17.1546	24.9904749	18	22.22222	33.33333	11.11111	33.33333	0
0.042643	14.3125	41.3857554	19	0	10.52632	0	84.21053	0
0.040892	21.19782	18.1624794	17	23.52941	23.52941	11.76471	41.17647	0
0.010542	24.15667	7.01444937	16	18.75	25	12.5	43.75	0
0.035965	17.39239	40.5299009	24	20.83333	20.83333	12.5	45.83333	0
0.064143	20.94903	38.49942	14	21.42857	14.28571	42.85714	14.28571	7.142857
0.042713	24.62435	12.3974396	14	14.28571	0	7.142857	78.57143	0
0.034602	24.42526	12.5146224	13	38.46154	38.46154	0	23.07692	0
0.145118	13.43841	56.1157598	36	44.44444	2.777778	13.88889	27.77778	0
0.01599	21.25534	17.3524062	15	20	6.666667	46.66667	20	6.666667
0.016812	24.96678	8.11055881	16	37.5	6.25	50	6.25	0
0.03769	15.76529	17.018881	17	47.05882	0	47.05882	0	5.882353
0.150851	12.70309	44.8167455	34	29.41176	11.76471	41.17647	14.70588	0

StepSeque	StepSeque	BOS_FrontI	BOS_HindP	OtherStat	OtherStat	OtherStat	OtherStat	OtherStat
0	87.5	1.449457	2.839372	2.5585	20.82686	81.91065	109	11.19644
0	82.75862	1.237563	2.618682	2.856	24.66262	112.9895	131	9.413009
0	68.8172	1.079026	2.08037	3.351	13.63405	95.13668	109	10.99413
0	68.08511	1.328229	2.359755	3.06	14.44771	60.31719	104	12.18586
0	94.11765	1.361051	2.930195	1.972	23.7336	35.85254	76	13.949
0	96.77419	1.357487	2.749619	2.185	20.83948	26.23882	73	11.81029
3.703704	69.67742	1.19529	2.715447	4.7852	10.45307	130.926	172	7.535849
0	92.75362	1.011666	2.386763	2.829333	17.41009	54.04917	79	9.703358
0	86.82171	1.165148	3.080324	2.9708	15.1006	85.04037	145	10.45274
0	80	1.338861	2.592575	4.212333	14.4336	212.7935	108	9.538836
0	83.80952	1.364857	2.893448	2.85475	15.6946	90.81681	118	11.09929
0	69.23077	1.490503	3.235305	3.9302	19.10203	131.2501	177	9.35004
0	89.15663	1.711121	3.012521	2.708333	16.37646	96.97177	186	12.07316
0	96.9697	1.479154	2.940915	1.525333	28.20669	31.47628	74	17.56227
18.75	72.72727	1.71189	3.005387	3.202667	14.17333	53.32494	101	11.02522
6.666667	96	1.505323	3.186944	1.7406	24.55337	42.59824	137	16.96864
0	98.63014	1.306339	3.007375	1.923333	22.79576	42.50536	81	14.81094
0	91.66667	1.329029	2.631956	1.4604	29.88287	36.99414	109	16.3272
0	84.375	1.252462	2.456521	3.615	25.57148	313.18	139	7.855838
0	92.30769	1.27061	2.968446	1.70225	27.79138	61.83631	98	17.1918
5	95.2381	1.385342	2.734415	4.277667	10.78106	86.8937	95	8.11375
8.333333	82.75862	1.330974	2.931016	1.632	26.65968	23.44965	72	15.78711
0	84.70588	1.510234	3.006871	2.902667	15.98936	64.0177	95	11.50809
5.263158	89.41176	1.683692	2.799347	3.988	12.62234	106.7927	95	8.220674
0	87.17949	1.593833	3.003466	2.107333	20.92494	44.07647	87	14.61659
0	96.9697	1.224613	3.247413	1.801333	24.80633	16.58462	77	15.03654
0	75.59055	1.486586	3.104137	3.1854	15.10074	110.6177	145	9.59438
0	91.80328	1.26509	2.967979	2.463	19.82307	60.24974	70	11.73476
0	91.80328	1.420043	2.648877	1.921	25.55916	23.08205	70	13.28376
0	89.65517	1.301358	2.840282	1.749333	24.39331	26.87354	66	13.45991
11.111111	89.44099	1.540333	3.176627	3.9442	13.0541	138.8931	176	9.551111
0	92.30769	1.447307	2.84642	2.008667	21.3719	46.87194	74	13.13806
0	94.11765	1.542931	2.951387	1.727	25.27105	24.92204	76	15.65248
0	82.92683	1.420519	3.128025	2.783333	15.48041	52.49726	91	11.61051
2.941176	87.17949	1.523014	3.596916	4.273	13.11137	115.1449	174	8.948484

OtherStat1: OtherStat1: OtherStat1: OtherStat1: OtherStat1: OtherStat1: OtherStat1: OtherStat1: OtherStat1:

-	-	-	0	0	0	0	0	0
-	-	-	0	0	0	0	0	0
-	-	-	0	0	0	0	10.91896	0
-	-	-	0	0	0	0	0	0
-	-	-	0	0	0	0	0	0
-	-	-	0	0	0	0	0	0
-	-	-	0	0	0	0	0.416586	0
-	-	-	0	0	0	0	0.235359	0
-	-	-	0	0	0	0	0	0
-	-	-	0	0	0	0	9.173622	0
-	-	-	0	0	0	0	0	0
-	-	-	0	0	0	0	0.253728	0
-	-	-	0	0	0	0	0	0
-	-	-	0	0	0	0	0	0
-	-	-	0	0	0	0	0	0
-	-	-	0	0	0	0	0	0
-	-	-	0	0	0	0	0	0
-	-	-	0	0	0	0	0	0
-	-	-	0	0	0	0	0	0
-	-	-	0	0	0	0	0	0
-	-	-	0	0	0	0	0	0
-	-	-	0	0	0	0	0	0
-	-	-	0	0	0	0	0	0
-	-	-	0	0	0	0	0.114662	0
-	-	-	0	0	0	0	0	0
-	-	-	0	0	0	0	0	0
-	-	-	0	0	0	0	0	0
-	-	-	0	0	0	0	0	0
-	-	-	0	0	0	0	0	0
-	-	-	0	0	0	0	0	0
-	-	-	0	0	0	0	0	0
-	-	-	0	0	0	0	1.216746	0
-	-	-	0	0	0	0	0	0
-	-	-	0	0	0	0	0	0
-	-	-	0	0	0	0	0	0
-	-	-	0	0	0	0	0.465799	0

OtherStat:	OtherStat:	PrintPositi	PrintPositi	PhaseDispe	PhaseDispe	PhaseDispe	PhaseDispe	PhaseDispe
0	0	0.840509	2.180479	5.690474	1.78978	0.729387	5.00592	2.964044
0	0	0.675271	1.214215	3.085545	98.55719	0.687181	7.096955	2.026827
0.595814	0	2.513357	2.243963	19.39144	12.46519	0.514099	20.82981	8.140943
0	0	0.550629	1.946496	10.7563	4.346696	0.67855	4.965807	5.154838
0	0	0.859988	1.416772	13.20285	8.83679	0.812721	1.409527	1.452153
0	0	1.151933	0.853081	-0.88727	0.07026	0.877986	-0.67918	99.41823
0	0	2.437557	2.26372	15.60437	2.828918	0.562299	16.13673	97.386
0	0	1.50757	0.522941	10.59117	7.969692	0.812766	99.34369	2.809635
0	0	1.899391	1.531105	-2.72159	95.86274	0.754577	7.543233	2.527522
0.474913	0	2.023908	2.123653	5.467239	1.268637	0.643736	8.909422	2.406075
0	0	0.992613	1.443182	19.29265	6.524932	0.572046	19.14283	5.472945
0	0	1.518052	2.489059	16.48765	93.80457	0.354615	10.73698	4.524654
0	0	1.203207	1.127902	1.732684	1.485491	0.80145	8.80858	3.277246
0	0	0.726587	0.611862	1.694465	1.75661	0.937134	-4.08934	95.92798
0	0	1.955696	2.200297	21.12159	9.041816	0.405757	23.92458	11.76036
0	0	0.724644	1.154545	3.087376	95.01795	0.641729	-1.93273	95.82246
0	0	0.544709	0.69628	-0.70873	95.9879	0.694472	2.589678	0.92462
0	0	0.793262	0.992465	-0.17292	96.35364	0.724214	-2.41753	97.60928
0.110174	0	0.288233	0.592815	94.31268	94.40022	0.858759	5.995262	1.806459
0	0	0.755224	0.678195	-1.42578	98.45517	0.890871	5.62137	97.45545
0	0	1.243357	1.130324	13.07003	7.575782	0.769383	6.844286	4.313849
0	0	2.370149	1.150105	-3.74181	96.20992	0.939187	17.61713	97.97768
0	0	2.475995	1.41121	101.011	2.265402	0.855951	20.52417	0.190335
0	0	1.509435	1.119021	13.8121	13.15318	0.858378	10.7926	5.880502
0	0	1.692046	0.926866	98.34459	0.987672	0.781297	18.97568	2.724375
0	0	0.797211	1.34697	8.93045	2.747145	0.679001	1.587396	1.495283
0	0	2.678257	2.267399	15.44025	0.66544	0.462628	18.26793	95.73408
0	0	0.91309	1.419499	-0.43435	95.2008	0.75194	98.25536	0.968394
0	0	1.156322	0.2409	3.320787	3.340026	0.983112	13.17339	2.125467
0	0	0.960148	0.346364	2.674051	2.714793	0.953498	12.11077	96.96772
0.303887	0	1.435643	1.253247	5.806452	1.003497	0.720316	12.23497	2.033373
0	0	0.856221	0.569326	-3.95882	96.06142	0.937882	10.42321	0.939013
0	0	0.73947	1.361476	4.219381	95.64207	0.736402	0.207759	0.284178
0	0	2.635114	1.341516	88.65529	88.69703	0.939368	19.40066	87.99243
0	0	1.580099	1.771783	-2.9954	94.66606	0.759249	6.946588	98.00647

| PhaseDispe |
|------------|------------|------------|------------|------------|------------|------------|------------|------------|
| 0.873108 | 38.1768 | 51.09717 | 0.613825 | 51.20482 | 51.33595 | 0.838798 | 45.14778 | 49.9698 |
| 0.651788 | 35.21621 | 52.95835 | 0.7481 | 44.68335 | 47.19671 | 0.786204 | 43.10579 | 56.10689 |
| 0.345341 | 36.26436 | 41.17114 | 0.494206 | 45.00778 | 45.91031 | 0.6421 | 34.59948 | 57.14659 |
| 0.860282 | 50.1765 | 50.1892 | 0.929991 | 39.78086 | 51.23615 | 0.384047 | 42.31626 | 56.40466 |
| 0.938977 | 48.52087 | 47.54926 | 0.895603 | 45.44106 | 45.45863 | 0.964686 | 55.72288 | 55.68319 |
| 0.893456 | 49.50526 | 49.51877 | 0.919578 | 52.68533 | 52.66239 | 0.95293 | 48.06719 | 48.12444 |
| 0.457913 | 32.43156 | 54.53133 | 0.307809 | 44.92762 | 48.56908 | 0.68952 | 43.04437 | 47.15209 |
| 0.606463 | 40.36098 | 44.71266 | 0.507744 | 50.64159 | 50.70587 | 0.953568 | 48.95079 | 51.92509 |
| 0.601547 | 32.95827 | 57.04273 | 0.465161 | 44.28031 | 51.59682 | 0.797941 | 39.16096 | 49.78926 |
| 0.694496 | 26.91939 | 50.70459 | 0.523893 | 53.22734 | 52.54635 | 0.820464 | 34.31207 | 45.74549 |
| 0.557359 | 27.56895 | 53.89032 | 0.352384 | 43.44495 | 44.24141 | 0.770419 | 52.38186 | 56.58894 |
| 0.682246 | 31.96631 | 46.03733 | 0.071943 | 49.35636 | 51.72723 | 0.742214 | 45.46295 | 51.26873 |
| 0.659495 | 33.58606 | 48.12422 | 0.593758 | 47.25422 | 54.82918 | 0.829023 | 41.44243 | 48.05015 |
| 0.958869 | 45.76551 | 45.7603 | 0.974596 | 48.37285 | 48.35227 | 0.963848 | 47.14354 | 47.14204 |
| 0.353156 | 16.93822 | 71.81487 | 0.169626 | 52.93933 | 52.83896 | 0.912921 | 40.27541 | 57.70765 |
| 0.787198 | 33.97978 | 53.45819 | 0.673658 | 45.0024 | 48.69483 | 0.88733 | 46.21119 | 47.89249 |
| 0.797643 | 40.67358 | 54.62442 | 0.606542 | 51.89148 | 51.73963 | 0.942574 | 49.76769 | 48.17265 |
| 0.953592 | 48.96026 | 49.11046 | 0.881491 | 48.40516 | 49.28852 | 0.836711 | 46.40125 | 46.38549 |
| 0.606296 | 31.08286 | 56.68407 | 0.661222 | 33.13648 | 52.86523 | 0.493093 | 40.34162 | 50.03483 |
| 0.636479 | 30.96536 | 50.43436 | 0.684655 | 40.04902 | 46.79894 | 0.826268 | 39.95257 | 49.0718 |
| 0.805645 | 36.27144 | 44.88136 | 0.581706 | 47.71087 | 47.7195 | 0.746828 | 39.69239 | 54.07142 |
| 0.298992 | 38.8955 | 53.2336 | 0.372001 | 49.42676 | 49.42539 | 0.940891 | 34.12854 | 48.91169 |
| 0.317033 | 29.89178 | 51.79526 | 0.363503 | 48.07366 | 48.05796 | 0.952982 | 40.20477 | 53.20586 |
| 0.751821 | 39.48439 | 49.51394 | 0.687387 | 44.69593 | 44.88056 | 0.899679 | 46.23543 | 60.45025 |
| 0.469396 | 28.80703 | 51.63522 | 0.413768 | 35.55774 | 54.21547 | 0.762146 | 42.25153 | 50.83266 |
| 0.940433 | 49.09109 | 48.92862 | 0.918544 | 50.87421 | 50.7824 | 0.951685 | 51.1181 | 51.1295 |
| 0.442377 | 14.55509 | 91.6732 | 0.041156 | 42.32848 | 49.96984 | 0.736703 | 35.60201 | 47.66004 |
| 0.830516 | 43.20588 | 54.89171 | 0.718735 | 50.60335 | 51.13722 | 0.875873 | 46.78723 | 49.48258 |
| 0.569621 | 36.12254 | 47.64812 | 0.621947 | 50.20142 | 50.18489 | 0.955315 | 44.70086 | 50.38708 |
| 0.629613 | 35.70638 | 47.44373 | 0.717187 | 48.74639 | 48.96843 | 0.884374 | 43.86736 | 49.73273 |
| 0.569059 | 38.04436 | 56.15198 | 0.488038 | 48.89914 | 50.11984 | 0.767523 | 37.84148 | 46.51352 |
| 0.61428 | 39.45199 | 53.00789 | 0.628946 | 52.63391 | 53.48031 | 0.879608 | 39.84604 | 49.01814 |
| 0.952194 | 56.6155 | 54.0256 | 0.794284 | 50.9428 | 50.92674 | 0.960322 | 48.97181 | 48.96972 |
| 0.3128 | 39.10759 | 51.49946 | 0.349637 | 54.38035 | 54.36363 | 0.95182 | 30.95217 | 38.97986 |
| 0.655295 | 42.52238 | 52.68025 | 0.539473 | 47.72168 | 51.60573 | 0.820938 | 39.01672 | 44.15184 |

PhaseDispe	PhaseDispe	PhaseDispe	PhaseDispe	Couplings_	Couplings_	Couplings_	Couplings_	Couplings_
0.816802	47.64467	53.51183	0.663574	44.85592	0.349391	0.709798	34.99278	2.637168
0.600888	41.33694	45.45151	0.661604	63.03389	97.8958	0.719716	57.98729	1.536569
0.32738	40.25648	65.94598	0.540133	32.74719	11.20384	0.445446	35.30941	6.507961
0.676001	41.13268	55.17162	0.347354	54.44511	0.720067	0.666008	104.4766	4.695034
0.95827	52.22865	54.7387	0.832036	26.53618	8.83679	0.812721	100.4232	0.509828
0.963987	51.32174	51.24179	0.915635	99.35861	99.65881	0.925193	99.87051	99.95943
0.504623	43.79551	49.60746	0.499103	33.46834	3.298113	0.560781	50.45622	97.63322
0.677155	54.82054	58.18979	0.848469	24.9282	8.016188	0.814943	99.61399	2.945388
0.617219	42.73098	44.12816	0.707672	56.87326	96.14979	0.785081	35.49744	2.70206
0.546276	42.38177	51.01014	0.45163	62.17946	1.407282	0.712571	41.73403	2.184682
0.62111	46.57868	53.88723	0.552417	26.07763	5.532853	0.567935	36.61865	4.330102
0.516686	36.86679	44.87981	0.327235	57.38738	93.02584	0.360118	33.16787	3.727404
0.648228	51.97656	54.82395	0.766263	57.00521	0.846681	0.851447	32.30712	2.75417
0.957059	50.37957	50.38473	0.970399	100.8835	0.945807	0.930152	95.27879	95.29585
0.369227	39.56971	60.69519	0.550454	26.13548	9.067196	0.406342	28.42426	11.90488
0.837809	37.9156	44.46244	0.694346	76.92582	96.18322	0.655168	68.09833	96.22825
0.794435	42.1794	46.76355	0.774049	66.43039	95.01492	0.691629	101.4791	99.82963
0.95679	42.21381	44.69958	0.807676	74.81037	96.65469	0.75289	96.44888	96.45727
0.721999	39.7047	45.30903	0.661771	93.82582	93.81396	0.87832	66.98118	1.0968
0.619458	43.65901	44.83876	0.901199	98.52417	98.44005	0.89569	81.40707	96.91327
0.606161	52.88496	57.93313	0.770905	32.45377	7.145487	0.776995	33.90482	3.124943
0.332566	44.74159	44.77095	0.976274	96.06663	96.03188	0.943412	69.08783	96.56666
0.348624	50.00847	51.63852	0.865915	101.3306	2.70378	0.853804	47.77084	0.327566
0.5438	57.5017	57.23005	0.834518	113.8121	13.15318	0.858378	26.34439	5.634053
0.524183	44.54578	53.47429	0.709846	98.68622	1.233533	0.796195	43.04418	2.483199
0.978341	40.67493	51.99535	0.686145	52.22851	2.060862	0.713353	101.5492	1.457719
0.456684	42.34197	51.77514	0.475458	40.43025	97.84481	0.457035	48.04265	96.94127
0.82823	42.49111	44.51081	0.782885	67.15699	94.78495	0.793079	98.13586	0.600079
0.627576	54.00065	53.97723	0.961073	102.3502	2.370485	0.974485	32.24838	2.851597
0.707643	50.58132	50.59356	0.95313	102.0978	2.102286	0.958073	58.03962	97.3146
0.566648	46.21513	49.90951	0.639618	60.10553	99.29859	0.675627	33.71329	2.259778
0.589761	47.91099	48.1431	0.927178	96.43073	96.46547	0.948607	55.65492	0.005749
0.98653	41.87992	46.78567	0.740301	80.9728	95.52927	0.76479	99.75557	99.78234
0.410277	42.55491	42.5487	0.95845	87.91744	87.99691	0.932062	61.2934	88.60218
0.558717	44.49446	45.08237	0.776726	71.12982	93.17364	0.737163	63.5079	98.02205

| Couplings_ |
|------------|------------|------------|------------|------------|------------|------------|------------|------------|
| 0.885256 | 99.23708 | 99.18633 | 0.920061 | 96.01461 | 95.97722 | 0.950498 | 52.30388 | 51.23987 |
| 0.688226 | 53.48541 | 97.54331 | 0.781968 | 63.60808 | 99.50679 | 0.832599 | 55.2027 | 54.03705 |
| 0.398587 | 75.64608 | 83.58034 | 0.533396 | 78.13128 | 91.54275 | 0.610596 | 46.87594 | 44.00084 |
| 0.856906 | 61.54529 | 94.37532 | 0.561111 | 72.49479 | 86.10519 | 0.566907 | 53.68587 | 51.20297 |
| 0.924852 | 90.94549 | 90.95472 | 0.935459 | 98.76046 | 98.7461 | 0.948368 | 48.48989 | 47.11168 |
| 0.918372 | 101.0799 | 0.768326 | 0.925159 | 100.98 | 0.960505 | 0.931048 | 49.50526 | 49.51877 |
| 0.458239 | 68.79794 | 93.24746 | 0.660977 | 64.19078 | 95.7687 | 0.620831 | 51.20525 | 54.39698 |
| 0.621926 | 82.63232 | 93.37757 | 0.821634 | 85.00652 | 84.93029 | 0.766374 | 40.36098 | 44.71266 |
| 0.623336 | 54.3168 | 1.722349 | 0.706181 | 75.80661 | 94.59473 | 0.666811 | 54.81366 | 58.24482 |
| 0.706944 | 66.34384 | 96.28891 | 0.690722 | 66.98748 | 93.54564 | 0.50377 | 48.13916 | 47.25035 |
| 0.580281 | 74.0238 | 88.32918 | 0.681006 | 64.07956 | 92.22445 | 0.673622 | 46.05809 | 52.41988 |
| 0.651231 | 45.2642 | 2.282563 | 0.629934 | 69.7723 | 93.47074 | 0.629187 | 45.27493 | 39.80472 |
| 0.703257 | 96.33999 | 97.69444 | 0.866214 | 75.49196 | 95.1804 | 0.778123 | 45.8739 | 47.10345 |
| 0.949737 | 98.65879 | 98.69432 | 0.934661 | 102.3347 | 2.393178 | 0.93408 | 45.76551 | 45.7603 |
| 0.362107 | 92.83041 | 92.8304 | 0.950666 | 80.63118 | 87.44574 | 0.809532 | 61.7787 | 84.44997 |
| 0.815552 | 103.2565 | 3.394863 | 0.889538 | 104.7512 | 4.796176 | 0.878536 | 55.82817 | 53.22408 |
| 0.807138 | 107.7141 | 7.78934 | 0.884429 | 101.4657 | 1.808542 | 0.902382 | 48.095 | 51.88984 |
| 0.948435 | 36.46679 | 4.716781 | 0.783506 | 101.3964 | 2.131039 | 0.886851 | 48.96026 | 49.11046 |
| 0.716471 | 39.47003 | 4.608024 | 0.475631 | 58.19505 | 2.070564 | 0.7733 | 61.2437 | 55.47721 |
| 0.683106 | 53.35779 | 0.338506 | 0.830923 | 103.6517 | 3.641122 | 0.970419 | 51.90595 | 49.24857 |
| 0.789748 | 90.66376 | 91.22751 | 0.849651 | 72.8822 | 95.71604 | 0.802832 | 45.97966 | 44.24954 |
| 0.397564 | 105.3963 | 5.397186 | 0.969791 | 101.3674 | 1.456991 | 0.908335 | 41.27858 | 52.35743 |
| 0.34739 | 94.15387 | 94.23552 | 0.885634 | 97.80024 | 97.30159 | 0.854667 | 48.45274 | 50.64466 |
| 0.742503 | 82.966 | 86.01123 | 0.744922 | 92.54473 | 92.84351 | 0.904351 | 53.86834 | 49.60609 |
| 0.49566 | 95.91995 | 96.19961 | 0.896318 | 93.65679 | 93.81146 | 0.879562 | 51.79255 | 49.8075 |
| 0.945895 | 84.67674 | 98.20591 | 0.716365 | 99.18368 | 99.2008 | 0.963724 | 48.59572 | 48.39955 |
| 0.464257 | 81.03669 | 88.55062 | 0.541291 | 62.29481 | 99.86604 | 0.698561 | 47.99892 | 9.628581 |
| 0.84017 | 105.5679 | 5.625522 | 0.927693 | 96.96453 | 97.12805 | 0.930311 | 58.25218 | 54.9441 |
| 0.570778 | 96.56676 | 96.54242 | 0.983768 | 92.75296 | 93.22155 | 0.871456 | 40.93647 | 47.02136 |
| 0.663655 | 97.79692 | 97.7989 | 0.949189 | 69.319 | 0.735391 | 0.768083 | 48.10949 | 47.16979 |
| 0.593613 | 52.92014 | 0.408476 | 0.758216 | 72.32979 | 93.53188 | 0.737721 | 54.99823 | 55.06784 |
| 0.669315 | 103.743 | 3.824504 | 0.935805 | 99.80671 | 99.80902 | 0.975752 | 55.45329 | 53.15182 |
| 0.960932 | 103.4349 | 3.420358 | 0.96248 | 100.7965 | 0.784021 | 0.960902 | 57.25296 | 53.80766 |
| 0.316989 | 11.68963 | 11.66468 | 0.939359 | 101.7279 | 1.187439 | 0.663541 | 46.90462 | 51.9548 |
| 0.708089 | 27.95116 | 8.86096 | 0.756926 | 50.38766 | 0.633768 | 0.86182 | 48.16627 | 53.11353 |

| Couplings_ |
|-------------------|-------------------|-------------------|-------------------|-------------------|-------------------|-------------------|-------------------|-------------------|
| 0.560943 | 50.46922 | 50.64067 | 0.847855 | 45.69599 | 47.00962 | 0.584561 | 46.63713 | 46.81683 |
| 0.642729 | 44.11155 | 46.70771 | 0.774668 | 41.50806 | 42.97853 | 0.625265 | 55.22004 | 53.74538 |
| 0.310336 | 45.00778 | 45.91031 | 0.6421 | 55.81034 | 58.76605 | 0.343201 | 53.34669 | 54.76766 |
| 0.763232 | 52.79678 | 53.26553 | 0.332603 | 43.36668 | 46.70753 | 0.477073 | 48.35946 | 48.72844 |
| 0.882151 | 45.44106 | 45.45863 | 0.964686 | 50.89236 | 53.35146 | 0.86924 | 54.19265 | 54.2277 |
| 0.919578 | 52.36435 | 52.32916 | 0.953057 | 50.9702 | 51.09699 | 0.934671 | 47.68473 | 47.69217 |
| 0.262267 | 49.31321 | 49.56945 | 0.630606 | 51.63077 | 91.52143 | 0.050805 | 50.97395 | 51.13425 |
| 0.507744 | 50.64159 | 50.70587 | 0.953568 | 58.39593 | 55.27552 | 0.648896 | 47.96949 | 48.20619 |
| 0.402574 | 52.59355 | 51.92878 | 0.703374 | 42.83142 | 41.67997 | 0.445715 | 48.69358 | 48.51771 |
| 0.344733 | 54.50986 | 53.4301 | 0.760955 | 49.40186 | 53.04494 | 0.356411 | 47.34498 | 43.24089 |
| 0.296822 | 43.10867 | 43.8589 | 0.765943 | 50.26357 | 48.00991 | 0.322825 | 52.39122 | 52.24279 |
| 0.05212 | 50.16638 | 52.39526 | 0.721576 | 48.06822 | 32.64317 | 0.164928 | 48.66337 | 47.63034 |
| 0.51705 | 53.55083 | 53.96968 | 0.860317 | 53.30648 | 52.89871 | 0.561388 | 46.36826 | 45.15454 |
| 0.974596 | 48.37285 | 48.35227 | 0.963848 | 53.17859 | 53.18224 | 0.981255 | 50.31759 | 50.40185 |
| 0.156013 | 52.93933 | 52.83896 | 0.912921 | 47.20234 | 9.406119 | 0.098503 | 47.70526 | 48.39362 |
| 0.650802 | 47.63003 | 48.0795 | 0.914636 | 46.9508 | 48.48934 | 0.63723 | 51.10877 | 50.79903 |
| 0.705511 | 51.74928 | 51.57883 | 0.939758 | 47.65405 | 45.62991 | 0.697448 | 47.90008 | 48.01145 |
| 0.881491 | 48.40516 | 49.28852 | 0.836711 | 50.33673 | 48.52951 | 0.694225 | 51.53842 | 50.80329 |
| 0.620269 | 52.99873 | 54.51795 | 0.43321 | 40.03002 | 41.24325 | 0.553696 | 48.79793 | 45.37004 |
| 0.674265 | 49.15139 | 45.90959 | 0.66723 | 51.34132 | 50.07289 | 0.530181 | 54.29275 | 51.85976 |
| 0.716534 | 49.12279 | 48.83211 | 0.701121 | 53.86623 | 53.09871 | 0.598612 | 50.96086 | 51.03628 |
| 0.443255 | 48.52375 | 48.5796 | 0.959402 | 59.14662 | 61.45052 | 0.246985 | 50.22827 | 50.20629 |
| 0.281348 | 50.23415 | 48.49727 | 0.851576 | 60.33634 | 62.04282 | 0.195562 | 50.17727 | 51.21317 |
| 0.673431 | 45.80669 | 45.16743 | 0.837351 | 45.62519 | 49.40483 | 0.681069 | 56.18088 | 55.55911 |
| 0.357422 | 50.22594 | 53.45721 | 0.698654 | 56.71905 | 51.03987 | 0.153927 | 49.21645 | 48.33778 |
| 0.921067 | 50.87421 | 50.7824 | 0.951685 | 50.06066 | 49.65874 | 0.80229 | 48.89115 | 48.98311 |
| 0.130678 | 54.09171 | 49.95663 | 0.722673 | 52.68303 | 54.15219 | 0.077119 | 53.29614 | 48.42884 |
| 0.599006 | 49.65438 | 50.21956 | 0.890212 | 45.57324 | 44.58886 | 0.557565 | 47.40876 | 47.37206 |
| 0.60522 | 50.10036 | 50.07755 | 0.952168 | 58.15458 | 53.91042 | 0.6555 | 48.89115 | 48.83331 |
| 0.698888 | 48.18842 | 48.37579 | 0.883478 | 51.51141 | 52.19573 | 0.715627 | 51.66678 | 51.61607 |
| 0.490234 | 49.43562 | 50.12499 | 0.723774 | 45.80495 | 44.87459 | 0.339651 | 47.34298 | 45.45831 |
| 0.60863 | 51.82911 | 52.70588 | 0.888541 | 59.25782 | 47.19793 | 0.408264 | 47.9539 | 47.79284 |
| 0.75664 | 50.52803 | 50.50788 | 0.961464 | 42.96424 | 46.83214 | 0.77035 | 49.15465 | 49.13446 |
| 0.327636 | 53.95928 | 53.93655 | 0.955207 | 57.83528 | 54.54549 | 0.31519 | 45.64513 | 45.63508 |
| 0.497778 | 51.06233 | 51.81424 | 0.789642 | 50.7195 | 46.72298 | 0.380291 | 47.6413 | 47.80647 |

| <u>Couplings_</u> |
|-------------------|-------------------|-------------------|-------------------|-------------------|-------------------|-------------------|-------------------|-------------------|
| 0.768605 | 51.17436 | 50.77284 | 0.758987 | 52.19013 | 53.51183 | 0.663574 | 46.62334 | 47.01351 |
| 0.785715 | 60.50897 | 57.0718 | 0.585813 | 48.23349 | 45.45151 | 0.661604 | 45.05555 | 45.14595 |
| 0.634182 | 59.86596 | 63.35566 | 0.187793 | 61.83533 | 68.59484 | 0.511544 | 41.77434 | 36.81282 |
| 0.417339 | 58.46656 | 58.09476 | 0.680707 | 54.48394 | 55.71729 | 0.298703 | 41.62634 | 42.05273 |
| 0.96521 | 55.72288 | 55.68319 | 0.95827 | 52.22865 | 54.7387 | 0.832036 | 45.14231 | 45.13638 |
| 0.948214 | 48.06719 | 48.12444 | 0.963987 | 51.32174 | 51.24179 | 0.915635 | 52.39268 | 52.40992 |
| 0.804977 | 47.11161 | 46.90616 | 0.466008 | 47.34904 | 50.56032 | 0.40889 | 53.88523 | 56.73403 |
| 0.926867 | 48.95079 | 51.92509 | 0.677155 | 54.82054 | 58.18979 | 0.848469 | 49.74265 | 49.0275 |
| 0.859857 | 52.605 | 50.07298 | 0.542075 | 45.49187 | 45.06623 | 0.611843 | 49.53277 | 49.02473 |
| 0.416622 | 47.93444 | 43.95272 | 0.373178 | 48.56323 | 52.54706 | 0.427685 | 57.3634 | 56.36346 |
| 0.669205 | 53.30413 | 57.55232 | 0.612463 | 46.36775 | 54.03904 | 0.534865 | 47.31248 | 46.98748 |
| 0.608433 | 49.31534 | 51.90668 | 0.485801 | 46.45749 | 45.75254 | 0.312337 | 47.6177 | 49.12947 |
| 0.655923 | 45.83723 | 49.3731 | 0.584442 | 54.67926 | 54.82395 | 0.766263 | 53.8865 | 51.8823 |
| 0.95163 | 47.14354 | 47.14204 | 0.957059 | 50.37957 | 50.38473 | 0.970399 | 52.24819 | 52.29946 |
| 0.819334 | 51.04525 | 59.52523 | 0.342416 | 53.83605 | 61.75026 | 0.492214 | 47.55513 | 42.81383 |
| 0.900568 | 49.78262 | 47.89249 | 0.837809 | 50.43362 | 44.43645 | 0.694325 | 49.6749 | 51.80631 |
| 0.915875 | 49.83383 | 48.12538 | 0.791012 | 50.29906 | 47.39076 | 0.685101 | 50.88514 | 52.08681 |
| 0.860883 | 46.40125 | 46.38549 | 0.95679 | 46.44458 | 44.84393 | 0.808192 | 53.01415 | 54.21898 |
| 0.631386 | 54.96366 | 50.04934 | 0.659468 | 43.96469 | 45.43373 | 0.66363 | 46.0866 | 50.05522 |
| 0.861409 | 53.60474 | 49.0468 | 0.619258 | 43.65901 | 44.83876 | 0.901199 | 51.57204 | 49.64927 |
| 0.696203 | 50.28664 | 55.33642 | 0.564079 | 60.08191 | 59.7701 | 0.730675 | 48.0499 | 45.4189 |
| 0.950581 | 50.81047 | 48.8664 | 0.33241 | 44.74159 | 44.77095 | 0.976274 | 66.06433 | 72.1408 |
| 0.872826 | 40.20477 | 53.20586 | 0.348624 | 50.00847 | 51.63852 | 0.865915 | 62.51282 | 69.6887 |
| 0.833934 | 55.07131 | 64.48822 | 0.441616 | 57.53848 | 57.22301 | 0.832237 | 43.23353 | 40.90324 |
| 0.878854 | 47.01343 | 50.83266 | 0.524183 | 50.97662 | 54.04901 | 0.646862 | 58.57702 | 55.0574 |
| 0.953202 | 51.1181 | 51.1295 | 0.978341 | 53.07901 | 52.03884 | 0.69153 | 48.85949 | 48.87975 |
| 0.580507 | 43.8743 | 47.61226 | 0.389572 | 50.33522 | 52.04801 | 0.429693 | 55.69622 | 55.92389 |
| 0.926656 | 46.78723 | 49.48258 | 0.82823 | 42.49111 | 44.51081 | 0.782885 | 51.24289 | 50.22927 |
| 0.97355 | 44.70086 | 50.38708 | 0.627576 | 54.00065 | 53.97723 | 0.961073 | 54.701 | 52.10083 |
| 0.935695 | 43.86736 | 49.73273 | 0.707643 | 50.58132 | 50.59356 | 0.95313 | 56.28314 | 50.03139 |
| 0.573457 | 47.77477 | 47.2788 | 0.496175 | 49.57611 | 50.5473 | 0.620353 | 52.35754 | 51.69277 |
| 0.918022 | 57.54933 | 48.92921 | 0.588481 | 47.91099 | 48.1431 | 0.927178 | 55.08078 | 50.59776 |
| 0.971862 | 48.97181 | 48.96972 | 0.98653 | 48.12992 | 46.78567 | 0.740301 | 51.14097 | 51.1362 |
| 0.95342 | 41.31237 | 37.87717 | 0.365759 | 42.55491 | 42.5487 | 0.95845 | 69.55218 | 78.84132 |
| 0.720017 | 46.52771 | 43.90413 | 0.486237 | 46.43287 | 46.18441 | 0.705834 | 57.53368 | 55.877 |

Couplings_	Couplings_	Couplings_	Couplings_	Support_Ze	Support_Si	Support_Di	Support_Gi	Support_La
0.848168	51.58972	49.19319	0.646733	0.409277	2.864939	61.52797	1.091405	2.728513
0.658728	57.38594	52.97592	0.688873	0.134409	4.704301	63.17204	1.075269	2.284946
0.442169	41.52824	35.18743	0.524249	0.843882	15.61181	46.27286	11.6737	2.109705
0.55506	50.34163	44.38622	0.368523	0	2.255639	44.21053	0.451128	0.451128
0.964559	47.87033	46.24405	0.82858	0	0	63.38798	0.273224	0.546448
0.972494	48.91316	48.9452	0.918953	0	1.809955	70.58824	0.678733	0
0.266141	58.53862	53.9602	0.475777	0.126422	2.465234	37.04172	1.074589	1.517067
0.797867	43.81774	42.51813	0.764616	0	1.123596	54.86891	1.310861	2.059925
0.504001	54.27587	54.72141	0.663243	0	0.689655	42.95567	0.197044	0.394089
0.509646	50.96382	46.35924	0.31579	0.107643	1.506997	34.44564	2.47578	0.430571
0.723091	48.6022	43.49589	0.481955	0	0.464037	51.74014	0.812065	1.160093
0.691043	53.78626	58.04449	0.274107	0	2.440633	32.78364	2.968338	0.791557
0.600481	47.05055	44.11969	0.65138	0.183824	0.735294	55.97426	0.367647	0.643382
0.931822	48.8072	48.77801	0.947348	0	1.25	81.25	1.875	0.625
0.456514	47.84075	43.23077	0.425338	0	4.920635	73.33333	4.603175	0.15873
0.808393	48.67101	52.96607	0.655933	0.3125	4.0625	72.65625	1.5625	1.875
0.810997	50.15648	51.66448	0.723896	0.229885	8.275862	74.94253	1.83908	1.37931
0.756211	53.28668	53.94426	0.845608	0	5.333333	70.66667	2	1.333333
0.340807	56.97066	56.49904	0.651031	0.245851	1.598033	19.6681	0.799017	0.307314
0.335523	55.4144	53.89307	0.891802	0	0.932401	62.47086	0.4662	0
0.638653	37.64822	39.2841	0.785623	0.421496	2.528978	54.16228	0.842993	2.002107
0.152555	55.44271	55.43945	0.966923	0	5.460751	83.27645	1.365188	3.754266
0.145153	49.44	48.08143	0.668691	0	3.500761	50.83714	0.608828	0.761035
0.622809	42.536	42.2891	0.854467	0	0.573888	56.81492	0.573888	0.573888
0.346033	48.66391	47.38176	0.825837	0	1.144165	70.70938	0.228833	1.830664
0.972644	46.80816	46.73491	0.836054	0.291545	9.037901	76.96793	2.623907	0.58309
0.443511	53.20674	43.23001	0.172457	0	1.255605	46.36771	2.152466	0.627803
0.736553	57.43946	56.44422	0.83069	0	3.205128	65.59829	1.495726	0
0.696018	44.66995	44.67201	0.986644	0	0	65.83541	0.249377	0.498753
0.65677	49.65879	49.66636	0.979048	0	1.358696	74.72826	1.358696	0.815217
0.477072	49.76538	51.08	0.521651	0	0.925926	37.30159	9.52381	0.132275
0.482988	52.68348	52.5884	0.928974	0	1.616628	80.60046	0.461894	2.309469
0.981368	58.64896	53.5028	0.705737	0	5.194805	69.61039	0	0.779221
0.181114	57.49488	57.54761	0.957404	0	4.96	59.2	0.8	2.08
0.422711	54.42978	56.4054	0.617678	0	1.766139	37.69793	0.426309	0.548112

Support_Tf Support_Four_(%)

17.73533	13.64256
17.60753	11.02151
22.78481	0.703235
38.49624	14.13534
33.87978	1.912568
20.58824	6.334842
31.09987	26.67509
36.70412	3.932584
34.6798	21.08374
36.38321	24.65016
34.91879	10.90487
30.73879	30.27704
25.36765	16.72794
14.0625	0.9375
15.71429	1.269841
14.21875	5.3125
11.95402	1.37931
12.44444	8.222222
12.78427	64.59742
13.98601	22.14452
24.76291	15.27924
6.143345	0
27.39726	16.89498
31.70732	9.756098
18.7643	7.322654
10.20408	0.291545
29.14798	20.44843
17.94872	11.75214
29.17706	4.239401
19.83696	1.902174
25.66138	26.45503
11.3164	3.69515
20.25974	4.155844
28.48	4.48
28.56273	30.99878

05-30-2019, CatWalk, Performed by Yun Li

Group	Cage #	Mice ID	Tail Bar	Animal	
Sham/WT (n=10)	Cage 1	J1	1	J1	
	Cage 6	J26	1	J26	
	old WT-1		1	1	1
			2	2	2
			3	3	3
			4	4	4
	old WT-2		5	no	5
			6	1	6
			7	2	7
			8	no	8
			<i>Mean</i>		
			<i>SEM</i>		
Sham/Hv1 KO (n=10)	Hv1-41	6677	1	6677	
		6678	no	6678	
	Hv1-42	6679	1	6679	
		6680	2	6680	
		6681	no	6681	
	old Hv1-8	792	no	792	
	old Hv1-9	793	no	793	
	Hv1-84	1	1	KO-1	
		2	2	KO-2	
		3	no	KO-3	
			<i>Mean</i>		
			<i>SEM</i>		
TBI/WT (n=8)	Cage 3	J11	1	J11	
		J12	2	J12	
		J14	4	J14	
	Cage 4	J16	1	J16	
		J17	2	J17	
		J18	3	J18	
		J19	4	J19	
		J20	no	J20	
				<i>Mean</i>	
				<i>SEM</i>	
TBI/Hv1 KO (n=8)	Hv1-34	6645	1	6645	
		6646	2	6646	
		6648	3	6648	

		6650	4	6650
	Hv1-36	6660	1	6660
		6663	2	6663
		6666	no	6666
			<i>Mean</i>	
			<i>SEM</i>	

Stride Length

Mean

Sham-WT
Sham-Hv1 KO
TBI-WT
TBI-Hv1 KO

SEM

Sham-WT
Sham-Hv1 KO
TBI-WT
TBI-Hv1 KO

RF_StrideLength_(cm)_Mean	RH_StrideLength_(cm)_Mean	LF_StrideLength_(cm)_Mean
6.420778902	5.541506636	6.129762768
6.628830695	5.287256066	6.852906518
3.786494325	3.848176805	5.291847114
5.279750621	5.316268252	3.775375985
6.470224448	6.452066822	6.394084207
6.597890741	6.72009102	6.556575769
4.664566831	4.085647832	5.445727211
6.769927011	5.234510406	5.961829824
5.522306313	4.810615156	5.989128769
5.134529454	4.361172358	4.206547075
5.73	5.17	5.66
0.32	0.30	0.32
5.635064523	5.11442673	5.537815341
5.305332095	4.55926667	4.874906913
5.456341622	4.759257077	4.952803359
6.732947457	6.649868775	6.686564361
6.176841475	4.00705251	5.804036413
6.165516451	5.859568392	6.123648469
6.148047401	5.755997806	6.05677912
6.94433066	7.638951328	7.348701686
5.055320599	6.058894212	6.119501657
6.346037931	5.778365388	7.153767896
6.00	5.62	6.07
0.20	0.34	0.26
5.30297282	4.769586674	5.264919887
7.492422323	4.840149866	7.443778324
5.68895253	3.987870211	5.559613858
4.967938255	4.559146747	5.516513755
5.657600232	4.81309084	6.313977075
6.530396648	6.533984585	6.500774012
6.861169701	4.693703291	6.000803031
7.562149491	6.71641364	7.455885264
6.26	5.11	6.26
0.35	0.34	0.30
7.23604981	5.634447662	7.248300202
7.329648368	6.338239468	7.350730143
4.796046303	4.487739198	4.47086111

6.94668415
6.626489878
5.905608408
4.897745771
6.25
0.40

5.680136101
6.571024431
3.828766767
4.109973504
5.24
0.41

7.037873831
6.662812439
6.028439048
4.758973531
6.22
0.45

RF
5.73
6.00
6.26
6.25

RH
5.17
5.62
5.11
5.24

LF
5.66
6.07
6.26
6.22

RF
0.32
0.20
0.35
0.40

RH
0.30
0.34
0.34
0.41

LF
0.32
0.26
0.30
0.45

LH_StrideLength_(cm)_Mean**StepSequence_RegularityIndex_(%)**

5.194056887
5.795206265
4.622714021
4.115057105
5.936321923
6.412941465
4.351056735
6.211920242
5.300977027
4.379130973
5.23
0.26

87.5
82.75862069
68.8172043
68.08510638
94.11764706
96.77419355
69.67741935
92.75362319
86.82170543
80
82.73
3.42

5.358686372
3.482520278
5.173218429
6.592802973
3.744675802
5.368289855
5.382766037
6.99822373
6.971337342
7.105878708
5.62
0.41

83.80952381
69.23076923
89.15662651
96.96969697
72.72727273
96
98.63013699
91.66666667
84.375
92.30769231
87.49
3.17

4.816752991
7.399626288
5.403395459
5.762032421
5.306981919
5.738113807
4.731649048
6.57685237
5.72
0.32

95.23809524
82.75862069
84.70588235
89.41176471
87.17948718
96.96969697
75.59055118
91.80327869
87.96
2.47

7.192715183
7.368799315
4.290433881

91.80327869
89.65517241
89.44099379

6.555170689
5.766862189
5.827235072
4.361122007
5.91
0.47

92.30769231
94.11764706
82.92682927
87.17948718
89.63
1.41

Step Sequence Regularity Inde

LH
5.23
5.62
5.72
5.91

LH
0.26
0.41
0.32
0.47

X

Print Positions

Sham-WT	Sham-Hv1 KO	TBI-WT	TBI-Hv1 KO
82.731	87.487	87.957	89.633
3.420	3.170	2.472	1.406

Sequence Regularity Index

Mean

- Sham-WT
- Sham-Hv1 KO
- TBI-WT
- TBI-Hv1 KO

SEM

- Sham-WT
- Sham-Hv1 KO
- TBI-WT
- TBI-Hv1 KO

PrintPositions_RightPaws_Mean_(cm)

PrintPositions_LeftPaws_Mean_(cm)

0.840509091
0.67527128
2.513356643
0.550629371
0.859988345
1.151933361
2.437557326
1.50756993
1.899390872
2.023908314
1.45
0.23

2.18047915
1.214215472
2.243962704
1.946496262
1.416772175
0.853080808
2.263719976
0.522941176
1.531104895
2.123653147
1.63
0.20

0.992613054
1.518051716
1.203206585
0.726586538
1.955696387
0.724643794
0.544708625
0.793261538
0.288232676
0.755224035
0.95
0.16

1.443181818
2.489059243
1.127902098
0.611862348
2.200297203
1.154545455
0.69627972
0.992465035
0.592814685
0.678194533
1.20
0.21

1.243356643
2.370148601
2.475994695
1.509434965
1.692046215
0.797211024
2.678257418
0.913090035
1.71
0.26

1.130324221
1.150104895
1.41120979
1.119020979
0.926865861
1.346969697
2.26739899
1.419498834
1.35
0.14

1.156321678
0.96014763
1.435643194

0.24090035
0.346363636
1.25324698

0.856220598
0.739470004
2.635113918
1.580099068
1.34
0.24

0.569326463
1.361475524
1.341516378
1.771783217
0.98
0.22

Right Paws

1.45
0.95
1.71
1.34

Left Paws

1.63
1.20
1.35
0.98

Right Paws

0.23
0.16
0.26
0.24

Left Paws

0.20
0.21
0.14
0.22

PhaseDispersions_RF->LH_Mean

PhaseDispersions_LF->RH_Mean

5.690473651
3.085545233
19.39144351
10.75629561
13.20285009
-0.88727425
15.60437001
10.59116718
-2.721589563
5.467238812
8.02
2.26

5.005920486
7.096954838
20.82981022
4.965806725
1.409526661
-0.67918295
16.13672931
99.34368533
7.543232662
8.909421974
17.06
9.36

19.29265104
16.48764973
1.73268406
1.69446524
21.12158687
3.087376338
-0.708729263
-0.172916263
94.31268475
-1.425775116
15.54
9.18

19.14283168
10.73698217
8.808579649
-4.089344739
23.9245782
-1.932731645
2.589677773
-2.417525265
5.995261549
5.621370494
6.84
2.91

13.07003377
-3.741814574
101.0110086
13.81209949
98.3445907
8.93044995
15.4402479
-0.434352847
30.80
15.22

6.844285616
17.61713325
20.5241708
10.79259571
18.9756794
1.587396056
18.26792972
98.25535531
24.11
10.85

3.320786964
2.674051235
5.806451891

13.17338572
12.11076963
12.23497403

-3.958824662	10.42321424
4.219381166	0.207758564
88.65528516	19.40066449
-2.995403174	6.946587561
13.96	10.64
12.53	2.24

Phase Dispersions

Mean

	RF->LH	LF->RH
Sham-WT	8.02	17.06
Sham-Hv1 KO	15.54	6.84
TBI-WT	30.80	24.11
TBI-Hv1 KO	13.96	10.64

SEM

	RF->LH	LF->RH
Sham-WT	2.26	9.36
Sham-Hv1 KO	9.18	2.91
TBI-WT	15.22	10.85
TBI-Hv1 KO	12.53	2.24

PhaseDispersions_LH->RH_Mean

PhaseDispersions_LF->RF_Mean

38.17679863
35.21620507
36.26435894
50.17649867
48.52087283
49.50526078
32.43156038
40.360979
32.95827303
26.91939217
39.05
2.53

51.20481983
44.68335449
45.00778347
39.78086472
45.44106045
52.68532509
44.9276247
50.64159485
44.28031314
53.2273436
47.19
1.40

27.5689548
31.96630922
33.58606474
45.76551232
16.93821822
33.97978015
40.67358356
48.9602639
31.08285971
30.96535535
34.15
2.91

43.44494566
49.3563647
47.25422422
48.37284797
52.93932704
45.00239569
51.8914831
48.40515869
33.13647809
40.0490248
45.99
1.87

36.2714365
38.89549965
29.89177563
39.48438753
28.80703
49.09109302
14.55509025
43.20588207
35.03
3.74

47.71086624
49.42676366
48.07366025
44.69592915
35.55774264
50.87420868
42.32847692
50.60335145
46.16
1.83

36.12253909
35.70637927
38.04435703

50.20142089
48.74638602
48.89913721

39.45198596
56.61550172
39.10758739
42.52237515
41.08
2.73

52.63390728
50.94279922
54.38034511
47.72168375
50.50
0.89

LH->RH
39.05
34.15
35.03
41.08

LF->RF
47.19
45.99
46.16
50.50

LH->RH
2.53
2.91
3.74
2.73

LF->RF
1.40
1.87
1.83
0.89

RF_PrintWidth_(cm)_Mean

0.594548148
0.681514403
0.457220231
0.802242798
0.815308642
0.797887517
0.627160494
0.804241104
0.781408075
0.749979424
0.71
0.04

0.694356261
0.737738791
0.678969404
0.759561043
0.679974009
0.687916667
0.627160494
0.792910053
0.711257015
0.713998101
0.71
0.01

0.598653199
0.791790123
0.749606114
0.737540741
0.658518519
0.772397661
0.766754281
0.807930283
0.74
0.03

0.870646333
0.776111111
0.715880759

0.822687001
0.792202729
0.733777778
0.758864198
0.78
0.02

Print Width

Mean

	RF
Sham-WT	0.71
Sham-Hv1 KO	0.71
TBI-WT	0.74
TBI-Hv1 KO	0.78

SEM

	RF
Sham-WT	0.04
Sham-Hv1 KO	0.01
TBI-WT	0.03
TBI-Hv1 KO	0.02

RH_PrintWidth_(cm)_Mean

LF_PrintWidth_(cm)_Mean

LH_PrintWidth_(cm)_Mean

0.646624095
0.637613169
0.352019116
0.909382716
0.829245542
0.839698217
0.540751715
0.689876543
0.739727762
0.642839506
0.68
0.05

0.574093067
0.660609053
0.594439077
0.576987654
0.770013717
0.815308642
0.741335866
0.683903586
0.803905724
0.687713921
0.69
0.03

0.501728395
0.707795414
0.321419753
0.73691358
0.61521458
0.8417154
0.637835566
0.677333333
0.865829904
0.722395976
0.66
0.05

0.740049383
0.61986793
0.883144369
0.766529492
0.367645807
0.771038489
0.671957672
0.883041975
0.697044092
0.739153439
0.71
0.05

0.721234568
0.680698585
0.669860783
0.775698506
0.635712682
0.642364385
0.61065627
0.792080476
0.764351852
0.783950617
0.71
0.02

0.681514403
0.547340067
0.662794613
0.878024691
0.461266428
0.741039636
0.606255144
0.823959132
0.822028219
0.803905724
0.70
0.04

0.576505223
0.627160494
0.746320988
0.75982906
0.687263374
0.61725796
0.65163505
0.807930283
0.68
0.03

0.635340848
0.726768337
0.710781893
0.708964037
0.719584146
0.67337232
0.745425044
0.800551924
0.72
0.02

0.629773663
0.693796296
0.83712292
0.746619636
0.755443322
0.705555556
0.719584146
0.818609487
0.74
0.02

0.815308642
0.874540466
0.73976431

0.815308642
0.780030864
0.704873859

0.909382716
0.834907407
0.702419753

0.793358025
0.749291748
0.658518519
0.81130549
0.78
0.03

0.867572016
0.723079158
0.840395062
0.77738731
0.79
0.02

0.887927225
0.791416814
0.83920047
0.801054994
0.82
0.03

RH
0.68
0.71
0.68
0.78

LF
0.69
0.71
0.72
0.79

LH
0.66
0.70
0.74
0.82

RH
0.05
0.05
0.03
0.03

LF
0.03
0.02
0.02
0.02

LH
0.05
0.04
0.02
0.03

RF_PrintLength_(cm)_Mean

RH_PrintLength_(cm)_Mean

0.72612028
0.758447552
0.509375141
0.914385198
0.860533677
0.884164724
0.70962306
0.764298643
0.86026838
0.844446387
0.78
0.04

0.679558717
0.695934343
0.316855403
0.932517483
0.925609946
0.908341103
0.558128982
0.618717949
0.830498476
0.721590909
0.72
0.06

0.808181818
0.839265734
0.844671633
0.856534577
0.765645933
0.812067308
0.736688811
0.87256993
0.748839797
0.851221087
0.81
0.02

0.835121212
0.803844528
0.895724276
0.908341103
0.493055221
0.808181818
0.674965035
0.855429371
0.744237762
0.799300699
0.78
0.04

0.697975207
0.866464161
0.905874126
0.823102098
0.76862047
0.87034965
0.860322581
0.899605101
0.84
0.03

0.681455083
0.62708422
0.721146853
0.925344271
0.74342366
0.742741995
0.774823469
0.92520362
0.77
0.04

0.921546689
0.916975524
0.829409858

0.808181818
0.89452603
0.851981882

0.92520362	0.823723776
0.883437615	1.086301067
0.864132867	0.67555711
0.881229021	0.869026931
0.89	0.86
0.01	0.05

Print Length

Mean

	RF	RH
Sham-WT	0.78	0.72
Sham-Hv1 KO	0.81	0.78
TBI-WT	0.84	0.77
TBI-Hv1 KO	0.89	0.86

SEM

	RF	RH
Sham-WT	0.04	0.06
Sham-Hv1 KO	0.02	0.04
TBI-WT	0.03	0.04
TBI-Hv1 KO	0.01	0.05

LF_PrintLength_(cm)_Mean

LH_PrintLength_(cm)_Mean

0.738840775	0.66240897
0.783314685	0.71048951
0.689252052	0.39631993
0.648617716	0.71715035
0.877257187	0.858508159
0.887618493	0.906341553
0.747608033	0.621678322
0.677925408	0.671412587
0.881652893	0.996412199
0.771738606	0.762131572
0.77	0.73
0.03	0.05

0.789531469	0.685918415
0.796051509	0.614896376
0.785695581	0.84350445
0.857261686	0.880165624
0.729059123	0.495337243
0.770504344	0.705114096
0.752557968	0.630559441
0.863442113	0.791032071
0.812067308	0.901433566
0.87034965	0.92121424
0.80	0.75
0.02	0.05

0.654113712	0.774507576
0.863035788	0.87034965
0.831864802	0.891973244
0.791964123	1.009487179
0.853989695	0.861872219
0.795093854	0.752230769
0.804629371	0.804909827
0.910575895	0.929245491
0.81	0.86
0.03	0.03

0.909204545	0.983028846
0.901433566	0.882006119
0.773043478	0.787459207

1.00504662
0.884977376
0.923192308
0.893481867
0.90
0.03

1.109205006
0.89995338
0.926596737
0.877414177
0.92
0.04

Single Stance

Mean

LF	LH
0.77	0.73
0.80	0.75
0.81	0.86
0.90	0.92

Sham-WT
Sham-Hv1 KO
TBI-WT
TBI-Hv1 KO

SEM

LF	LH
0.03	0.05
0.02	0.05
0.03	0.03
0.03	0.04

Sham-WT
Sham-Hv1 KO
TBI-WT
TBI-Hv1 KO

RF_SingleStance_(s)_Mean

RH_SingleStance_(s)_Mean

LF_SingleStance_(s)_Mean

0.141548423
0.114827158
0.081560516
0.092318196
0.123027086
0.135887875
0.149164561
0.158526136
0.130003747
0.145964314

0.13
0.01

0.138345827
0.096388978
0.11579265
0.120649118
0.10736781
0.117236787
0.132409271
0.109838941
0.076382155
0.086207447

0.11
0.01

0.141450077
0.107329845
0.156936172
0.091448014
0.112847653
0.150601579
0.199542133
0.162619673
0.154800179
0.112189582

0.14
0.01

0.151617014
0.116059325
0.125849482
0.099923121
0.163942053
0.110731184
0.129177306
0.100659801
0.06290948
0.08310565

0.11
0.01

0.119300048
0.112531265
0.102863159
0.101168807
0.122546413
0.100353546
0.124803128
0.107961225
0.070981757
0.074552826

0.10
0.01

0.129239795
0.126065734
0.110798353
0.105913556
0.161242854
0.103750486
0.126861156
0.104305103
0.108064025
0.100255076

0.12
0.01

0.189589055
0.131069724
0.146860229
0.134126978
0.10804075
0.120489204
0.191272202
0.136189886

0.14
0.01

0.164656098
0.071932667
0.083213809
0.129590911
0.088324746
0.097225417
0.099279526
0.110440657

0.11
0.01

0.186460003
0.125037551
0.120365551
0.135885204
0.139041322
0.123615799
0.129142994
0.153326576

0.14
0.01

0.138822654
0.145062912
0.102599103

0.089747026
0.108399094
0.096842367

0.136030956
0.137364121
0.12736651

0.150576304
 0.119084461
 0.153757513
 0.135713783
 0.14
 0.01

0.107702902
 0.103149044
 0.077962776
 0.093404424
 0.10
 0.00

0.149177102
 0.118532119
 0.167250048
 0.164359285
 0.14
 0.01

3

RF
 0.13
 0.11
 0.14
 0.14

RH
 0.11
 0.10
 0.11
 0.10

LF
 0.14
 0.12
 0.14
 0.14

RF
 0.01
 0.01
 0.01
 0.01

RH
 0.01
 0.01
 0.01
 0.00

LF
 0.01
 0.01
 0.01
 0.01

LH_SingleStance_(s)_Mean**RF_PrintArea_(cm²)_Mean**

0.117381907
0.109485926
0.107917247
0.102871554
0.090390668
0.115528734
0.10519331
0.155166308
0.121705528
0.114372219
0.11
0.01

0.241421178
0.277603163
0.132940623
0.373484125
0.39399621
0.418050956
0.278915483
0.293107107
0.383991014
0.342617668
0.31
0.03

0.108203129
0.074490023
0.088729973
0.095921852
0.106695657
0.083477596
0.10539164
0.087085153
0.086338523
0.085270658
0.09
0.00

0.339763101
0.37203913
0.356920774
0.384043702
0.310682428
0.308258428
0.232570628
0.34770019
0.282051477
0.336056984
0.33
0.01

0.160965792
0.136527938
0.120841091
0.151748656
0.106572056
0.10154924
0.104119939
0.115529876
0.12
0.01

0.230568
0.347735002
0.401774509
0.378819148
0.3174076
0.364241288
0.406871255
0.421312798
0.36
0.02

0.128905179
0.124322646
0.099655571

0.427963898
0.412310878
0.35993696

0.1479085
0.080904557
0.134136976
0.102700533
0.12
0.01

0.436449785
0.393585798
0.38365381
0.40655997
0.40
0.01

Print Area

	Mean	
LH		RF
0.11	Sham-WT	0.31
0.09	Sham-Hv1 KO	0.33
0.12	TBI-WT	0.36
0.12	TBI-Hv1 KO	0.40

	SEM	
LH		RF
0.01	Sham-WT	0.03
0.00	Sham-Hv1 KO	0.01
0.01	TBI-WT	0.02
0.01	TBI-Hv1 KO	0.01

RH_PrintArea_(cm²)_Mean LF_PrintArea_(cm²)_Mean LH_PrintArea_(cm²)_Mean

0.241733092	0.257178816	0.18472818
0.232419003	0.290469602	0.291527881
0.055087978	0.197827853	0.069530755
0.387942623	0.25459953	0.284899715
0.410253114	0.394874038	0.318226205
0.427365045	0.391841544	0.419031386
0.173112085	0.315412698	0.185903864
0.231707295	0.259928055	0.208787211
0.387292803	0.407141854	0.460180962
0.265683605	0.328316023	0.305126656
0.28	0.31	0.27
0.04	0.02	0.04

0.343624889	0.338296364	0.262787264
0.287885434	0.341963886	0.228051424
0.409784536	0.338459511	0.336724981
0.431047359	0.392559766	0.441604086
0.106077536	0.27540559	0.10891824
0.335192517	0.302579886	0.277952014
0.203672198	0.237628964	0.16282636
0.329536789	0.36043357	0.308552528
0.271587685	0.319224143	0.380562523
0.343662022	0.358169046	0.397512701
0.31	0.33	0.29
0.03	0.01	0.03

0.212641144	0.23393525	0.234422615
0.220882341	0.331637619	0.306065285
0.29202917	0.363899278	0.327000795
0.239783631	0.35836168	0.267725897
0.272924458	0.374501606	0.353915677
0.260612077	0.307399127	0.261617588
0.294320975	0.336532567	0.360444971
0.417643226	0.415579091	0.395432655
0.28	0.34	0.31
0.02	0.02	0.02

0.383765208	0.415966116	0.498818184
0.442960728	0.40012675	0.435704403
0.387765399	0.30962517	0.318411868

0.404902928
0.431343768
0.293718703
0.435102974

0.438628594
0.401130149
0.385018432
0.422534211

0.531689678
0.383765208
0.403074149
0.385904551

0.40
0.02

0.40
0.02

0.42
0.03

RH
0.28
0.31
0.28
0.40

LF
0.31
0.33
0.34
0.40

LH
0.27
0.29
0.31
0.42

RH
0.04
0.03
0.02
0.02

LF
0.02
0.01
0.02
0.02

LH
0.04
0.03
0.02
0.03

RF_InitialDualStance_(s)_Mean

RH_InitialDualStance_(s)_Mean

0.057496832
0.029175631
0.045581348
0.065029584
0.029267769
0.016663413
0.085531342
0.033081362
0.02864988
0.099017883
0.05
0.01

0.023857063
0.015122124
0.005205499
0.077632186
0.03755992
0.046649208
0.147396218
0.051931831
0.070946461
0.084168673
0.06
0.01

0.05421702
0.122733599
0.040427617
0.007491965
0.031007192
0.015665181
0.006248826
0.0142813
0.097785918
0.005221898
0.04
0.01

0.031827724
0.152994808
0.030626045
0.019984527
0.011435838
0.014619207
0.004370539
0.026271281
0.004597802
0.013300811
0.03
0.01

0.072331309
0.002135874
0.021146381
0.050754332
0.005541526
0.004995893
0.112859325
0.039193498
0.04
0.01

0.092800295
0.005771205
0.02478668
0.037025802
0.037470879
0.011984336
0.030885682
0.05799859
0.04
0.01

0.016864036
0.015380896
0.103408904

0.032825593
0.029320765
0.118804495

0.010001863	0.013879862
0.007844295	0.018630415
0.007040286	0.020689265
0.119634747	0.118758484
0.04	0.05
0.02	0.02

Initial Dual Stance

Mean

	RF	RH
Sham-WT	0.05	0.06
Sham-Hv1 KO	0.04	0.03
TBI-WT	0.04	0.04
TBI-Hv1 KO	0.04	0.05

SEM

	RF	RH
Sham-WT	0.01	0.01
Sham-Hv1 KO	0.01	0.01
TBI-WT	0.01	0.01
TBI-Hv1 KO	0.02	0.02

LF_InitialDualStance_(s)_Mean

LH_InitialDualStance_(s)_Mean

0.010431393
0.009965375
0.050920377
0.031630088
0.014343146
0.026672976
0.146890348
0.039943519
0.076691778
0.055556778
0.05
0.01

0.062173508
0.088756716
0.003176336
0.027128797
0.023073103
0.033122717
0.047861983
0.053771959
0.085807139
0.118399739
0.05
0.01

0.031091896
0.074550679
0.028110368
0.001997638
0.034586137
0.004803003
0.008820731
0.009969088
0.243729919
0.049741303
0.05
0.02

0.086975905
0.05456029
0.068336336
0.009991998
0.008121052
0.024306317
0.023317089
0.017696725
0.473035922
0.064697252
0.08
0.04

0.060395046
0.003835572
0.058838061
0.046691573
0.036924059
0.008119031
0.01515838
0.011408852
0.03
0.01

0.042075224
0.007674996
0.085841037
0.057593911
0.008926997
0.008328417
0.118353353
0.032800351
0.05
0.01

0.021346376
0.006920732
0.034717339

0.032735511
0.017647613
0.060183217

0.014986275
0.011228082
0.019365805
0.049566216

0.018658099
0.030994632
0.078692818
0.108833941

0.02
0.01

0.05
0.01

Max Intensity

Mean

LF
0.05
0.05
0.03
0.02

LH
0.05
0.08
0.05
0.05

Sham-WT
Sham-Hv1 KO
TBI-WT
TBI-Hv1 KO

SEM

LF
0.01
0.02
0.01
0.01

LH
0.01
0.04
0.01
0.01

Sham-WT
Sham-Hv1 KO
TBI-WT
TBI-Hv1 KO

RF_MaxIntensity_Mean	RH_MaxIntensity_Mean	LF_MaxIntensity_Mean
109.56	126.7931034	119.1153846
132.0333333	122.1111111	127.8
73.67741935	46.03225806	71
158.4583333	168.5	136.8
175.9473684	179.5555556	170.9444444
182.6111111	198.4444444	178.5555556
145.3414634	146.1333333	150.2051282
143.1764706	140	129.2380952
180.7297297	187.7179487	190.3333333
145.2916667	158.1071429	152.4137931
144.68	147.34	142.64
10.72	13.83	10.87
149.0714286	164.9	144.4
165.3684211	161.9534884	167.9512195
158.8478261	181.877551	165
161.8888889	188.4444444	158.3157895
123.2105263	83.13793103	117.7272727
132.5625	164.5294118	143.5454545
128.1	127	134.0526316
142.5357143	178.24	160.6296296
134.9772727	166.4857143	141.28125
149.9230769	172.9285714	151.4545455
144.65	158.95	148.44
4.66	9.92	4.89
140.6818182	104.1153846	143.0869565
146.875	151.5652174	154.5882353
156.1428571	162.9666667	160.1904762
162.12	150.5769231	168.7391304
145.2727273	175.6666667	171.1578947
168.3157895	168.2631579	149.9473684
169.3870968	184.804878	156.6285714
182	182.0588235	164.2352941
158.85	160.00	158.57
5.02	9.17	3.35
164.1764706	176.2380952	169.3125
167	192.7777778	175.8125
156.8292683	179.4545455	149.5

176.1176471	191.25	157.0555556
174.4736842	161.2631579	163.0588235
159.2	165.6666667	164.6
187.425	196.0851064	182.7674419
169.32	180.39	166.02
4.06	5.16	4.23

RF	RH	LF
144.68	147.34	142.64
144.65	158.95	148.44
158.85	160.00	158.57
169.32	180.39	166.02

RF	RH	LF
10.72	13.83	10.87
4.66	9.92	4.89
5.02	9.17	3.35
4.06	5.16	4.23

LH_MaxIntensity_Mean**BOS_FrontPaws_Mean_(cm)**

116.6206897

1.449457105

131.5142857

1.23756311

46.375

1.079025758

143.75

1.328228674

176.7142857

1.361051273

192.7894737

1.35748723

137.7234043

1.195289937

129.6

1.011665677

194.6111111

1.165147938

166.4444444

1.338860581

143.61

1.25

13.82

0.04

154.3

1.364857206

157.6363636

1.490503241

144.7045455

1.711120543

183.6842105

1.479154392

90.09677419

1.711889563

160.4736842

1.505323023

134.7619048

1.306339318

174.7931034

1.329029106

185.25

1.252462298

185.2272727

1.270609739

157.09

1.44

9.29

0.05

119.1666667

1.385341673

171.3125

1.330973937

175.0434783

1.510233756

139.4285714

1.683692089

187.7272727

1.593832609

167.9

1.224613385

180.4736842

1.48658606

172.3157895

1.265089878

164.17

1.44

8.14

0.06

189.1875

1.420043397

195.375

1.301358025

173.1333333

1.540332792

193.3157895
 157.5238095
 160.952381
 186.0681818
 179.37
 5.87

1.447307231
 1.542930956
 1.420518519
 1.523013503
 1.46
 0.03

Base of Support

LH	Mean	Front Paws
143.61	Sham-WT	1.25
157.09	Sham-Hv1 KO	1.44
164.17	TBI-WT	1.44
179.37	TBI-Hv1 KO	1.46

LH	SEM	Front Paws
13.82	Sham-WT	0.04
9.29	Sham-Hv1 KO	0.05
8.14	TBI-WT	0.06
5.87	TBI-Hv1 KO	0.03

BOS_HindPaws_Mean_(cm)**OtherStatistics_NumberOfSteps**

2.839372317	109
2.618682142	131
2.080369814	109
2.359754725	104
2.930194908	76
2.749618507	73
2.715446761	172
2.386762693	79
3.080323653	145
2.592574553	108
2.64	110.60
0.09	10.02
2.893447662	118
3.235305282	177
3.01252063	186
2.940914565	74
3.005386884	101
3.186944186	137
3.007375003	81
2.631955887	109
2.456520814	139
2.968446185	98
2.93	122.00
0.07	11.94
2.734415002	95
2.93101619	72
3.006871119	95
2.799347067	95
3.003466303	87
3.247412533	77
3.104136947	145
2.967978967	70
2.97	92.00
0.06	8.42
2.648877322	70
2.840281634	66
3.176627336	176

2.846420356	74
2.951387419	76
3.128025203	91
3.596915542	174
3.03	103.86
0.12	18.60

Number of Steps

	Sham-WT	Sham-Hv1 KO
Hindpaws		
2.64	110.600	122.000
2.93	10.019	11.936
2.97		
3.03		

Hindpaws
0.09
0.07
0.06
0.12

OtherStatistics_Cadence

11.19643599
9.413008993
10.99413324
12.18585898
13.94899526
11.8102918
7.535849263
9.703358453
10.4527428
9.538835587
10.68
0.56

11.0992944
9.350040271
12.07315686
17.5622709
11.02522462
16.96863683
14.81093825
16.32720387
7.855838497
17.19179671
13.43
1.13

8.113750179
15.78710619
11.50809036
8.220674182
14.61659107
15.03653663
9.594379951
11.73476394
11.83
1.08

13.28375757
13.45991284
9.5511115

13.13806213
15.65248258
11.61050811
8.948484473
12.23
0.89

Cadence

TBI-WT	TBI-Hv1 KO
92.000	103.857
8.420	18.604

Mean	Sham-WT	Sham-Hv1 KO	TBI-WT
	10.678	13.426	11.826
SEM	0.562	1.130	1.083

RF_MaxContactArea_(cm²)_Mean

0.186680329
0.223668092
0.098227651
0.305740375
0.332844715
0.351119482
0.223379635
0.229806981
0.314231944
0.276660924
0.25
0.02

0.289216377
0.309964206
0.313100295
0.324910069
0.25363506
0.259400077
0.200794423
0.280861547
0.23490998
0.270075247
0.27
0.01

0.184312621
0.272437093
0.338649124
0.323766386
0.270797774
0.307809539
0.326628948
0.345857213
0.30
0.02

0.352967009
0.335063509
0.30268939

0.362828986
0.333460334
0.320491292
0.366108666
0.34
0.01

Max Contact Area

TBI-Hv1 KO

12.235
0.893

Mean

Sham-WT
Sham-Hv1 KO
TBI-WT
TBI-Hv1 KO

RF

0.25
0.27
0.30
0.34

SEM

Sham-WT
Sham-Hv1 KO
TBI-WT
TBI-Hv1 KO

RF

0.02
0.01
0.02
0.01

RH_MaxContactArea_(cm²)_Mean

LF_MaxContactArea_(cm²)_Mean

0.206373913
0.18617347
0.043391216
0.309432535
0.340505753
0.347437167
0.143740215
0.189376155
0.32151101
0.216529353
0.23
0.03

0.206492846
0.24329266
0.139852595
0.213011041
0.336390225
0.322960609
0.246331819
0.202001232
0.358346269
0.282873429
0.26
0.02

0.283191616
0.233209869
0.341513637
0.363899278
0.074751724
0.302166364
0.17433746
0.269805322
0.225357624
0.278912087
0.25
0.03

0.286830609
0.289185811
0.301212373
0.347003954
0.217453448
0.262999933
0.19166274
0.296029174
0.262689791
0.290824049
0.27
0.01

0.156706626
0.184096871
0.255639243
0.189997411
0.23361034
0.226342615
0.240306657
0.35824202
0.23
0.02

0.189521456
0.267420099
0.30764342
0.283265074
0.335101985
0.262869347
0.266686185
0.334848495
0.28
0.02

0.340691416
0.38945887
0.324585159

0.347247637
0.322392016
0.246818641

0.349148361
0.290777412
0.247711437
0.374628223
0.33
0.02

0.310614026
0.35159092
0.315032803
0.364322416
0.32
0.01

RH
0.23
0.25
0.23
0.33

LF
0.26
0.27
0.28
0.32

RH
0.03
0.03
0.02
0.02

LF
0.02
0.01
0.02
0.01

LH_MaxContactArea_(cm²)_Mean

0.148562328
0.241733092
0.050523516
0.22850461
0.261042033
0.348029986
0.149901063
0.165899081
0.368231412
0.251841405
0.22
0.03

0.20456338
0.185021516
0.291887391
0.385172337
0.081625794
0.249120521
0.1346056
0.254102082
0.30926797
0.330699376
0.24
0.03

0.178700538
0.25879087
0.259193476
0.200144603
0.30003968
0.223408164
0.294573729
0.325457286
0.26
0.02

0.437410181
0.38867367
0.27136489

0.438936403
0.304301488
0.326024047
0.331674106
0.36
0.02

Max Contact

Mean

LH
0.22
0.24
0.26
0.36

Sham-WT
Sham-Hv1 KO
TBI-WT
TBI-Hv1 KO

SEM

LH
0.03
0.03
0.02
0.02

Sham-WT
Sham-Hv1 KO
TBI-WT
TBI-Hv1 KO

RF_MaxContactMaxIntensity_Mean**RH_MaxContactMaxIntensity_Mean**

106.24	123.8965517
124.1	116.8888889
69.35483871	42.96774194
140.3333333	163.4090909
165.4210526	174.7222222
175.8333333	193.3888889
135.0731707	140.1777778
140.9411765	132.6190476
166.7027027	182.4615385
140	152.6785714
136.40	142.32
9.96	13.65
144.0714286	159.4
155.3157895	155
144.6086957	177.122449
151.8333333	182.2777778
117.5789474	78.37931034
124.53125	160.2352941
125.55	124.6666667
138.8571429	173.92
128.6818182	163.0857143
140.0384615	168.2857143
137.11	154.24
3.96	9.81
126.9545455	95.15384615
142.125	148.3478261
142.7142857	156.9333333
138.92	120.0769231
137.9090909	169.4166667
154.4736842	164.3157895
159.5806452	174.4146341
171.6470588	177.3529412
146.79	150.75
5.02	10.24
154.4705882	171.7142857
155.6875	184.5
142.4390244	172.8409091

163
154.5263158
146.3
174
155.77
3.95

186.05
153.0526316
157.1666667
190.0212766
173.62
5.43

Max Intensity

RF
136.40
137.11
146.79
155.77

RH
142.32
154.24
150.75
173.62

RF
9.96
3.96
5.02
3.95

RH
13.65
9.81
10.24
5.43

LF_MaxContactMaxIntensity_Mean**LH_MaxContactMaxIntensity_Mean**

113.2692308	110.6551724
121.7666667	125.3428571
66.56521739	40.95833333
126.2	140.1071429
162.1666667	173.4285714
160.2222222	186.8947368
141.1282051	126.3404255
126.0952381	123.3
174.6060606	186.1111111
143.2413793	162.7037037
133.53	137.58
9.73	13.84
139.5666667	147.2333333
156.902439	152.3636364
152.2553191	132.2045455
153.0526316	180.8421053
109.5	82.83870968
138.2121212	157
129.8421053	130.5714286
151.6296296	166.8965517
133.5	176.75
146.6363636	179.1818182
141.11	150.59
4.54	9.47
128.5652174	101.7916667
142.8823529	164.875
148.6666667	168.4782609
158.6086957	123.2380952
159.1578947	181.0909091
143.1578947	165.55
147.7142857	170.2631579
154.0588235	158.5263158
147.85	154.23
3.54	9.59
159.375	184.6875
164.1875	193.375
141.1304348	167.4666667

149.6111111
151.8235294
150.9
175.5581395
156.08
4.27

177.2105263
149.047619
150.5238095
178.8409091
171.59
6.36

LF
133.53
141.11
147.85
156.08

LH
137.58
150.59
154.23
171.59

LF
9.73
4.54
3.54
4.27

LH
13.84
9.47
9.59
6.36

Support_Zero_ (%)	Support_Single_ (%)	Support_Diagonal_ (%)
0.409276944	2.864938608	61.52796726
0.134408602	4.704301075	63.17204301
0.843881857	15.61181435	46.27285513
0	2.255639098	44.21052632
0	0	63.38797814
0	1.809954751	70.58823529
0.12642225	2.465233881	37.04171934
0	1.123595506	54.86891386
0	0.689655172	42.95566502
0.107642626	1.506996771	34.44564047
0.16	3.30	51.85
0.09	1.43	3.95
0	0.464037123	51.74013921
0	2.440633245	32.78364116
0.183823529	0.735294118	55.97426471
0	1.25	81.25
0	4.920634921	73.33333333
0.3125	4.0625	72.65625
0.229885057	8.275862069	74.94252874
0	5.333333333	70.66666667
0.24585126	1.59803319	19.6681008
0	0.932400932	62.47086247
0.10	3.00	59.55
0.04	0.81	6.31
0.421496312	2.528977871	54.16227608
0	5.460750853	83.27645051
0	3.500761035	50.83713851
0	0.573888092	56.81492109
0	1.14416476	70.70938215
0.29154519	9.037900875	76.96793003
0	1.255605381	46.367713
0	3.205128205	65.5982906
0.09	3.34	63.09
0.06	0.99	4.65
0	0	65.83541147
0	1.358695652	74.72826087
0	0.925925926	37.3015873

0	1.616628176	80.60046189
0	5.194805195	69.61038961
0	4.96	59.2
0	1.766138855	37.69792935
0.00	2.26	60.71
0.00	0.76	6.51

Patterns of Stance

Mean

	Zero	Single	Diagonal
Sham-WT	0.162	3.303	51.847
Sham-Hv1 KO	0.10	3.00	59.55
TBI-WT	0.09	3.34	63.09
TBI-Hv1 KO	0.00	2.26	60.71

SEM

	Zero	Single	Diagonal
Sham-WT	0.09	1.43	3.95
Sham-Hv1 KO	0.04	0.81	6.31
TBI-WT	0.06	0.99	4.65
TBI-Hv1 KO	0.00	0.76	6.51

Support_Girdle_ (%)	Support_Lateral_ (%)	Support_Three_ (%)	Support_Four_ (%)
1.091405184	2.72851296	17.73533424	13.6425648
1.075268817	2.284946237	17.60752688	11.02150538
11.67369902	2.109704641	22.78481013	0.70323488
0.45112782	0.45112782	38.4962406	14.13533835
0.273224044	0.546448087	33.87978142	1.912568306
0.678733032	0	20.58823529	6.334841629
1.074589128	1.517067004	31.09987358	26.67509482
1.310861423	2.059925094	36.70411985	3.93258427
0.197044335	0.39408867	34.67980296	21.08374384
2.475780409	0.430570506	36.38320775	24.65016146
2.03	1.25	29.00	12.41
1.09	0.31	2.65	2.96
0.812064965	1.160092807	34.9187935	10.90487239
2.968337731	0.791556728	30.73878628	30.27704485
0.367647059	0.643382353	25.36764706	16.72794118
1.875	0.625	14.0625	0.9375
4.603174603	0.158730159	15.71428571	1.26984127
1.5625	1.875	14.21875	5.3125
1.83908046	1.379310345	11.95402299	1.379310345
2	1.333333333	12.44444444	8.222222222
0.799016595	0.307314075	12.78426552	64.59741856
0.466200466	0	13.98601399	22.14452214
1.73	0.83	18.62	16.18
0.41	0.19	2.68	6.20
0.842992624	2.002107482	24.76290832	15.27924131
1.365187713	3.754266212	6.14334471	0
0.608828006	0.761035008	27.39726027	16.89497717
0.573888092	0.573888092	31.70731707	9.756097561
0.228832952	1.830663616	18.76430206	7.322654462
2.623906706	0.583090379	10.20408163	0.29154519
2.152466368	0.627802691	29.14798206	20.44843049
1.495726496	0	17.94871795	11.75213675
1.24	1.27	20.76	10.22
0.29	0.43	3.24	2.63
0.249376559	0.498753117	29.17705736	4.239401496
1.358695652	0.815217391	19.83695652	1.902173913
9.523809524	0.132275132	25.66137566	26.45502646

0.461893764	2.309468822	11.31639723	3.695150115
0	0.779220779	20.25974026	4.155844156
0.8	2.08	28.48	4.48
0.426309379	0.548112058	28.56272838	30.99878197
1.83	1.02	23.33	10.85
1.29	0.32	2.49	4.65

Girdle	Lateral	3-Paw	4-Paw
2.030	1.252	28.996	12.409
1.73	0.83	18.62	16.18
1.24	1.27	20.76	10.22
1.83	1.02	23.33	10.85

Girdle	Lateral	3-Paw	4-Paw
1.09	0.31	2.65	2.96
0.41	0.19	2.68	6.20
0.29	0.43	3.24	2.63
1.29	0.32	2.49	4.65

RF_SwingSpeed_(cm/s)_Mean

RH_SwingSpeed_(cm/s)_Mean

45.62024221
79.15808159
43.18135044
42.64029682
59.38633519
46.2105737
28.63424606
45.65113268
43.39341677
42.70465514
47.66
4.20

45.92575109
48.29385057
27.11761064
39.18364939
67.74052965
56.0612922
29.96353862
43.84671588
43.95263852
47.15520394
44.92
3.71

42.69792681
46.76227429
46.64089813
59.24739821
36.35955113
54.15941033
45.64120757
66.79317313
53.79233652
74.17536357
52.63
3.64

42.8375118
41.2379177
54.85748743
69.87592032
28.84707169
60.76818243
48.46153843
76.75534003
70.73747306
78.73192708
57.31
5.32

30.14945988
56.63603819
46.15919145
40.60659062
51.14885109
52.96087183
46.59537503
50.05696061
46.79
2.93

26.01885415
43.44136777
37.36572651
34.60312791
42.08519101
46.40137895
41.22981652
54.17950487
40.67
2.95

56.52413001
53.64057299
37.05662871

53.31294135
53.81469922
42.67508587

46.46019943	43.3248991
56.5427938	70.86146225
35.08168216	34.51289194
34.10836925	40.81267361
45.63	48.47
3.84	4.54

Swing Speed

Mean

	RF	RH
Sham-WT	47.66	44.92
Sham-Hv1 KO	52.63	57.31
TBI-WT	46.79	40.67
TBI-Hv1 KO	45.63	48.47

SEM

	RF	RH
Sham-WT	4.20	3.71
Sham-Hv1 KO	3.64	5.32
TBI-WT	2.93	2.95
TBI-Hv1 KO	3.84	4.54

LF_SwingSpeed_(cm/s)_Mean**LH_SwingSpeed_(cm/s)_Mean**

46.0921162	41.57425244
54.5839974	60.05000552
54.68394638	21.20204109
58.56261778	39.34555452
53.73063409	57.77989485
49.75784037	57.15752337
32.46640223	34.47550198
42.61717819	46.04661593
44.26105319	61.98059922
40.65183894	47.29304407
47.74	46.69
2.53	4.12
40.55761468	41.11967482
53.16728943	35.91709802
45.9040859	46.00141715
62.87929818	65.95931537
40.36962622	26.70880375
51.7732234	52.35322469
46.18943831	45.16680565
68.80837444	68.5481527
78.09912907	82.72158818
72.82352655	82.68788866
56.06	54.72
4.33	6.13
29.74401791	28.61285806
53.28761825	65.62696351
39.72672566	47.5916366
38.07425884	37.76553851
51.74539261	50.65979393
52.98361128	52.24011363
40.03780912	41.94848647
53.74851286	55.39315092
44.92	47.48
3.24	4.02
57.25845693	65.67825501
51.93968526	56.48458581
49.88594849	44.8400095

48.73698424
56.68791837
39.62617699
38.4933569
48.95
2.82

51.6569221
60.71783428
49.42253447
43.43025477
53.18
3.11

LF
47.74
56.06
44.92
48.95

LH
46.69
54.72
47.48
53.18

LF
2.53
4.33
3.24
2.82

LH
4.12
6.13
4.02
3.11

OtherStatistics_Average_Speed_Mean

20.82686006
24.66261973
13.63405211
14.44771117
23.73359974
20.83947888
10.45307147
17.41008646
15.10060289
14.43360402
17.55
1.50

15.69459959
19.10202704
16.37646438
28.20668507
14.17333139
24.55337484
22.79576482
29.8828696
25.57148056
27.79137543
22.41
1.81

10.78106035
26.65968087
15.98936114
12.62234261
20.92494384
24.80632745
15.10073544
19.82306941
18.34
2.01

25.55916425
24.39330808
13.05410272

21.37190215
25.27105131
15.48041346
13.11136817
19.75
2.16

Average Speed

	Sham-WT	Sham-Hv1 KO	TBI-WT	TBI-Hv1 KO
Mean	17.554	22.415	18.338	19.749
SEM	1.496	1.806	2.008	2.158

Couplings_RF->LH_Mean

44.85592228
63.03388655
32.74719306
54.44511438
26.53618342
99.35861354
33.46834165
24.92819509
56.87326323
62.17945854
49.84
7.15

26.07762949
57.38737875
57.00521434
100.8834507
26.13547576
76.92582139
66.43039284
74.81037301
93.82582445
98.52416797
67.80
8.53

32.4537714
96.06663178
101.3305508
113.8120995
98.68621651
52.22851441
40.43025381
67.1569908
75.27
11.01

102.3502029
102.0978236
60.10553016

96.43073466
80.97280423
87.91743752
71.12982105
85.86
6.09

Couplings

Mean

	RF->LH
Sham-WT	49.84
Sham-Hv1 KO	67.80
TBI-WT	75.27
TBI-Hv1 KO	85.86

SEM

	RF->LH
Sham-WT	7.15
Sham-Hv1 KO	8.53
TBI-WT	11.01
TBI-Hv1 KO	6.09

Couplings_LF->RH_Mean	Couplings_LH->RH_Mean	Couplings_LF->RF_Mean
34.99277688	52.30388374	50.46922444
57.98728542	55.20269554	44.11154772
35.30940771	46.87594156	45.00778347
104.4765766	53.68587435	52.79678412
100.4232424	48.48988775	45.44106045
99.87051336	49.50526078	52.36434676
50.45621672	51.20524848	49.31320652
99.61399154	40.360979	50.64159485
35.49744189	54.81366135	52.5935491
41.73402727	48.13915568	54.50985536
66.04	50.06	49.72
9.82	1.41	1.16
36.6186544	46.05808596	43.10866941
33.1678707	45.27492787	50.16638263
32.30711941	45.87389752	53.55082603
95.27878713	45.76551232	48.37284797
28.42425851	61.77869646	52.93932704
68.09832804	55.82816797	47.63003227
101.4791274	48.09499776	51.74928413
96.44888195	48.9602639	48.40515869
66.98118159	61.24370053	52.99872522
81.40706716	51.90594644	49.15138964
64.02	51.08	49.81
9.27	2.02	1.01
33.90481976	45.97966123	49.12279128
69.08782745	41.27858296	48.52374924
47.77084314	48.45273934	50.23415408
26.34438894	53.86834256	45.80668865
43.04417654	51.79254995	50.22594336
101.5491669	48.59571661	50.87420868
48.04264564	47.99892068	54.09171369
98.13585975	58.25217836	49.65438449
58.48	49.53	49.82
10.03	1.82	0.82
32.24837881	40.93646996	50.10036468
58.03961748	48.10949316	48.18841572
33.71329298	54.99823008	49.43562168

55.65492223
99.75557165
61.29340221
63.50790063
57.74
8.51

55.45328677
57.25295531
46.90461518
48.16626999
50.26
2.21

51.82910894
50.52803428
53.95927944
51.06232703
50.73
0.70

LF->RH
66.04
64.02
58.48
57.74

LH->RH
50.06
51.08
49.53
50.26

LF->RF
49.72
49.81
49.82
50.73

LF->RH
9.82
9.27
10.03
8.51

LH->RH
1.41
2.02
1.82
2.21

LF->RF
1.16
1.01
0.82
0.70

Run_Maximum_Variation_(%)_Mean

59
57.8
42
65
22
14
83.6
42.66666667
55.8
89.33333333
53.12
7.58

40.25
59
80.5
25.66666667
25.33333333
32
40.66666667
32.2
97.4
54.25
48.73
7.66

59.66666667
14.66666667
42.66666667
75.33333333
39.33333333
11.66666667
68.2
67
47.32
8.64

21
24.66666667
72

29.66666667
13.33333333
33.66666667
65.8
37.16
8.57

Run Maximum Variation

	Sham-WT	Sham-Hv1 KO	TBI-WT	TBI-Hv1 KO
Mean	53.120	48.727	47.317	37.162
SEM	7.584	7.662	8.643	8.574

RF_TerminalDualStance_(s)_Mean

0.014729542
0.009969188
0.055226154
0.076597423
0.014633745
0.025334865
0.119056332
0.045563115
0.077854771
0.083000176
0.05
0.01

0.03188912
0.081327363
0.032620767
0.002497551
0.035991377
0.004631467
0.009372026
0.009535649
0.202830966
0.045004036
0.05
0.02

0.058373491
0.002137877
0.067522342
0.042590072
0.033206627
0.008119031
0.016142742
0.011407545
0.03
0.01

0.026052172
0.006920732
0.049955807

0.01398719
0.011407734
0.019365805
0.052886946
0.03
0.01

Terminal Dual Stance

Mean

	RF
Sham-WT	0.05
Sham-Hv1 KO	0.05
TBI-WT	0.03
TBI-Hv1 KO	0.03

SEM

	RF
Sham-WT	0.01
Sham-Hv1 KO	0.02
TBI-WT	0.01
TBI-Hv1 KO	0.01

RH_TerminalDualStance_(s)_Mean

LF_TerminalDualStance_(s)_Mean

0.071584831

0.05397607

0.086727235

0.035761744

0.003038235

0.096062698

0.03883782

0.062534459

0.028750617

0.027439983

0.036663731

0.01666628

0.044313572

0.109541602

0.042442974

0.032100372

0.077826585

0.029593056

0.13205316

0.075939724

0.06

0.05

0.01

0.01

0.086212567

0.05381413

0.068566294

0.122765367

0.066427508

0.041009777

0.011866285

0.007991429

0.008489658

0.030483551

0.02659372

0.015506827

0.027479064

0.005881248

0.018605806

0.014931359

0.284898792

0.117343101

0.060191179

0.005771572

0.07

0.04

0.03

0.01

0.047388938

0.075613183

0.006306172

0.002300172

0.065435442

0.03573147

0.049365968

0.056144392

0.008076807

0.007629163

0.009994101

0.004371262

0.072953503

0.100835587

0.089287729

0.039194805

0.04

0.04

0.01

0.01

0.027543926

0.015659462

0.013969418

0.015380896

0.070214282

0.105897329

0.016103014
0.040584229
0.056152646
0.108367974

0.05
0.01

0.010001403
0.008110074
0.009386255
0.112899829

0.04
0.02

RH

0.06
0.07
0.04
0.05

LF

0.05
0.04
0.04
0.04

RH

0.01
0.03
0.01
0.01

LF

0.01
0.01
0.01
0.02

LH_TerminalDualStance_(s)_Mean**RF_StepCycle_(s)_Mean**

0.020719491
0.046001267
0.005442113
0.059398966
0.038035386
0.039354999
0.136852643
0.064527088
0.082442206
0.118013651
0.06
0.01

0.358138374
0.274546542
0.316195476
0.383509347
0.278074764
0.335195597
0.537638736
0.394432177
0.371275397
0.474435641
0.37
0.03

0.035282171
0.127589457
0.032387185
0.021316023
0.012174696
0.015884919
0.005551277
0.025361804
0.005750527
0.052339351
0.03
0.01

0.370185771
0.458866427
0.348924426
0.223149013
0.42235919
0.241093014
0.28544111
0.230723082
0.410794142
0.220215583
0.32
0.03

0.093287046
0.009197916
0.034959642
0.04264286
0.040891952
0.010542171
0.035965278
0.064142534
0.04
0.01

0.516783966
0.269248804
0.352275742
0.461299776
0.270327234
0.259717292
0.470866324
0.314487482
0.36
0.04

0.042713184
0.034601826
0.145117761

0.30977256
0.30626789
0.40961173

0.01598995
0.016812015
0.037690002
0.150850844
0.06
0.02

0.329077978
0.255779826
0.349175065
0.484487119
0.35
0.03

Step Cycle

	Mean	RF
LH		
0.06	Sham-WT	0.37
0.03	Sham-Hv1 KO	0.32
0.04	TBI-WT	0.36
0.06	TBI-Hv1 KO	0.35

	SEM	RF
LH		
0.01	Sham-WT	0.03
0.01	Sham-Hv1 KO	0.03
0.01	TBI-WT	0.04
0.02	TBI-Hv1 KO	0.03

RH_StepCycle_(s)_Mean LF_StepCycle_(s)_Mean LH_StepCycle_(s)_Mean

0.350720863	0.349601193	0.331981792
0.393333011	0.298656322	0.264818817
0.2856657	0.442272369	0.348088929
0.373024549	0.275060873	0.289875415
0.262670599	0.280647941	0.253803249
0.321781126	0.324453678	0.321068204
0.492089799	0.620526731	0.440334309
0.313437305	0.368359509	0.402971135
0.333894343	0.408281696	0.373911893
0.407537953	0.378346996	0.411153423
0.35	0.37	0.34
0.02	0.03	0.02

0.34591859	0.355948371	0.355915524
0.411616222	0.409245494	0.34077935
0.28056926	0.319275247	0.311474402
0.22581468	0.219827337	0.223573664
0.259575542	0.377759658	0.264130629
0.236142853	0.244606829	0.217806169
0.267363701	0.283941779	0.252394927
0.251898094	0.239436942	0.233250547
0.56459783	0.60774253	0.7130037
0.210997362	0.256924551	0.2591428
0.31	0.33	0.32
0.03	0.04	0.05

0.462494217	0.507905351	0.468519523
0.173495382	0.267848798	0.26854597
0.26442921	0.36224251	0.361470559
0.439075133	0.382301082	0.404282643
0.233168557	0.306601197	0.256612654
0.259717289	0.258469176	0.224451693
0.36415065	0.417770089	0.358284945
0.329409875	0.337954155	0.321318719
0.32	0.36	0.33
0.04	0.03	0.03

0.245358804	0.312894005	0.322860225
0.264096805	0.307026311	0.305493187
0.416265932	0.391936893	0.386144532

0.27041667
0.255156078
0.242393187
0.414976089
0.30
0.03

0.32711427
0.255993377
0.348590638
0.450743812
0.34
0.02

0.303548983
0.225732335
0.361903714
0.441518796
0.34
0.03

RH
0.35
0.31
0.32
0.30

LF
0.37
0.33
0.36
0.34

LH
0.34
0.32
0.33
0.34

RH
0.02
0.03
0.04
0.03

LF
0.03
0.04
0.03
0.02

LH
0.02
0.05
0.03
0.03

RF_DutyCycle_(%)_Mean	RH_DutyCycle_(%)_Mean	LF_DutyCycle_(%)_Mean
48.5937921	58.45092263	53.13314748
54.36605825	57.57867658	48.83792805
56.00669429	46.00040431	64.54575828
62.89297438	59.26566613	63.56976464
58.3262847	62.36522719	54.94407965
54.95922219	60.91659463	57.20925849
62.56051315	55.82379951	62.7520704
57.35856397	57.04967255	59.84338158
60.074789	61.27788004	60.5211881
56.8546279	60.98756488	58.89254261
57.20	57.97	58.42
1.33	1.49	1.57
61.52018549	61.36454807	57.20043316
62.45142345	58.37470645	64.60852186
57.1600288	61.99228834	57.7287381
47.94287149	57.32914305	50.60434819
58.47563019	49.38659827	57.8273674
50.96923794	56.95532879	49.4932781
48.53093712	51.31850238	48.62847395
53.61658629	57.72006782	51.24485427
57.84387779	54.50905254	58.43749466
54.64513557	57.72452108	52.50792712
55.32	56.67	54.83
1.60	1.26	1.61
57.24356239	52.51511233	57.60828126
50.46660419	43.98596208	47.23213908
60.19308918	55.47909066	56.53095316
60.9191964	56.78739776	58.11363656
54.80498709	51.80602293	56.7873713
51.46600914	44.62414013	51.87147834
59.11388836	60.65427124	56.02068328
50.31881449	58.99817129	55.78609673
55.57	53.11	54.99
1.56	2.19	1.29
54.39583196	56.80073158	54.0671378
53.74095633	55.93295804	52.02998885
54.90441627	60.46737309	61.01678184

52.15022651	51.86974342	53.17848294
53.50372017	62.52916232	53.47846334
51.15693997	56.12747435	55.33554149
58.68888648	66.36804652	64.90658154
54.08	58.59	56.29
0.91	1.83	1.81

Duty Cycle

Mean

	RF	RH	LF
Sham-WT	57.20	57.97	58.42
Sham-Hv1 KO	55.32	56.67	54.83
TBI-WT	55.57	53.11	54.99
TBI-Hv1 KO	54.08	58.59	56.29

SEM

	RF	RH	LF
Sham-WT	1.33	1.49	1.57
Sham-Hv1 KO	1.60	1.26	1.61
TBI-WT	1.56	2.19	1.29
TBI-Hv1 KO	0.91	1.83	1.81

LH_DutyCycle_(%)_Mean

53.35470526
57.29938366
35.66162755
61.33038351
58.534742
63.18544281
60.28006843
63.89393066
71.9345879
64.54856469
59.00
3.03

58.49996327
55.46221922
56.66099572
54.36717671
50.17026233
54.99492729
49.62169526
54.41857963
58.71879588
59.10165487
55.20
1.05

56.77505719
57.51814021
62.9164375
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57.12112097
49.73417751
55.35578126
60.62462486
57.46
1.40

61.75053002
54.82734627
70.70866279

57.44578907
57.50867978
65.74496004
69.94690315
62.56
2.41

LH
59.00
55.20
57.46
62.56

LH
3.03
1.05
1.40
2.41